
D2.5 / Updated report on user research and co-creation

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List of abbreviations

AI	Artificial intelligence
Apo	Apomorphine
GP	General practitioner
HCP	Healthcare professional
ICG	Informal caregiver
iRBD	Idiopathic REM sleep behavior disorder
KPI	Key performance indicator
mHealth	Mobile health
MVP	Minimum viable product
PD	Parkinson's disease
PwoP	People without Parkinson's disease, such as ICGs and persons at risk for PD
PwP	Person with Parkinson's disease
R&D	Research and development
UI/UX	User interface/User experience
WP	Work package

Executive summary

The purpose of deliverable D2.5 “Updated report on user research and co-creation” is to provide an updated documentation on stakeholders and potential user needs and methods employed in research and developing new digital solutions. The deliverable clarifies and expands on user needs and prototype feedback imperative for the co-design, and presents it by the tools the project is developing. Different forms of co-creation between developers and users are described, with considerations for co-creation in healthcare application development. As a background, the current status for diagnosis of Parkinson's Disease (PD) and care pathways for people with PD (PwP) are defined through four countries: France, Germany, Spain, and the United Kingdom (UK).

Qualitative and quantitative methods have been used to gather data to inform the design process and enhance user experiences of the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem of digital health tools for advancing PD diagnosis and care. User research is an iterative process that plays a pivotal role in shaping user-centric solutions, ensuring that the end product aligns seamlessly with the expectations and preferences of its intended users. Collected data have provided user needs for the solutions of AI-PROGNOSIS, i.e., the mAI-Health mobile app for persons without PD, the mAI-Care mobile app for PwP, and the mAI-Insights platform and the AI-assisted medication decision support module for healthcare professionals, and are coded, described, and prioritised at the end of the report.

This is an updated version of Deliverable D2.1 ‘Initial report on user research and cocreation’, under T2.2 ‘User research and co-creation’, and adds all relevant information collected during 1/7/2024-13/6/2025 to the previous version.

1 Introduction

1.1 Document scope

D2.5 “Updated report on user research and co-creation” is an updated version of D2.1 “Initial report on user research and co-creation”. It falls under Task 2.2 “User research and co-creation” which aims to define the needs of relevant stakeholders and effectively engage them in developing tailored AI-driven tools for PD risk assessment, monitoring and prognosis.

The report defines the user research and co-creation process within the project and presents the findings of the secondary and primary user research, with emphasis on the needs, requirements, and concerns of stakeholders regarding the tools for PD screening and care that AI-PROGNOSIS aims to develop. Certain sections and content of D2.1 are also included here for the sake of completeness.

1.2 Document structure

This report is structured into six additional sections:

- 1) The background (Section 2) is provided for the current status of PD diagnosis and PwP care pathways within selected countries (where AI-PROGNOSIS clinical partners are based), as well as an overview of gender differences within PD and PwP’s needs from digital technology.
- 2) Section 3 introduces the common methods of user research and co-creation.
- 3) Section 4 defines user research and co-creation within the project.
- 4) Section 5 provides secondary research findings, as well as primary user research findings from focus groups, interviews, workshops, and surveys.
- 5) The identified user needs within the project are described in Section 6.
- 6) Section 7 concludes the report.

At the end of the report, [four](#) Appendices present the focus group protocol, the healthcare professionals’ (HCP) interview guide, protocols for workshops, the surveys, the checklist for co-creation with focus on patients and informal caregivers (ICGs) as partners, and the personas for HCPs, PwP, and people without PD (PwoP), including ICGs and at-risk individuals.

2 Background

2.1 Current status for PD diagnosis and care pathways

The current status for PD diagnosis and care is described for the four countries where AI-PROGNOSIS clinical partners are based, i.e., France, Germany, Spain and United Kingdom (UK). There is little evidence about the education level of PwP, as well as their abilities regarding the use of technology, apart from the UK, where patients are described having high abilities of using technology. Levodopa is one of the most common treatments, and the number of visits for clinical assessment differs between the different study sites within the countries from one to four annual visits.

2.1.1 France

2.1.1.1 Characteristics of patients

Numbers of PwP, distribution Male/Female, age distribution and other demographics

There are approximately 200.000 PD patients in France, with an average disease onset of 58 years (10% < 40 years old) and a ratio of male to female is 1.5:1. Annually, 25,000 new patients receive the diagnosis (Institute Pasteur, 2020).

Where do they live?

PD patients are equally distributed in rural areas and cities.

Education level

There is no specific data on educational level of French PD patients.

Technological abilities

Similarly for educational level, no data for technological abilities are available for French patients. AI-PROGNOSIS patient panel members (see Section 4) expressed that in their experience, French PD patients may be reluctant for technology use, including applications (apps), tele-visits/telemedicine and wearable sensors. The sole exception is the use of easy-to-use wearable sensors (e.g., the PKG¹ or Sense4Care² or FeetMe³) for which patients can be helped by healthcare providers with home visits. However, a 2020-2021 web-based survey in France found that the majority (1,239 out of 2,003 respondents, 62%) considered the use of mHealth apps useful but only 27.6% (551 out of 2,003) found video recording/broadcasting useful. Age (≤ 55 years), trust in political representatives, and higher health literacy were factors associated with the perceived usefulness of both technologies (Touzani et al., 2023).

2.1.1.2 Characteristics of the healthcare system

How is care for PD delivered?

PD patients are principally followed by neurologists, both community-based neurologists and hospital-based ones, who frequently collaborate (one visit/year with each one of those physicians). Concomitantly, one epidemiological study in 2017 showed that only 33.5% of PD patients had received a neurology consultation over a one-year study period (Carriere et al., 2017), whereas a neurology consultation every 6 months is the recommended standard of care in the French national protocol for diagnosis and management (PNDS).

How is care for PD funded?

Care for PD is funded by the National healthcare system, even if the pharmaceutical industry's contribution to research protocol is allowed and frequently used.

What does the journey to a PD diagnosis look like in France?

The diagnosis journey depends on whether a patient lives in cities or rural areas. For the latter, access to a specialist for diagnosis may require travel to a city, as the number of specialists may be limited. This can delay diagnosis and treatment. However, in the city this is less of an issue.

What does the standard practice for PD care look like?

The standard practice of care for PD patients is two visits/year, including one in tertiary hospital. Access to PD nurses and educational therapies programs is possible; however, mainly in university hospitals.

¹ PKG Health - <https://pkghealth.com/>

² Sense4Care - <https://www.sense4care.com/pages/products/>

³ FeetMe - <https://feetmehealth.com/>

Available treatments

All oral/transdermal treatments (with the exception of Safinamide, Opicapone, and of Rivastigmine that is available but not reimbursed) and all advanced treatments (Brinker et al., 2023), such as deep brain stimulation (Okun, 2012), Gamma-Knife (Higuchi et al., 2017), apomorphine (apo) pump (Katzenschlager et al., 2018) and Levodopa–carbidopa intestinal gel (LCIG) (Olanow et al., 2014), with the exception of Magnetic resonance (MR)-guided focused ultrasound (MRgFUS) (Martínez-Fernández et al., 2020). Subcutaneous levodopa pumps (Soileau et al., 2022) will be available at the end of 2024.

Most common treatments

The most common pharmacological treatments are oral dopamine agonists, levodopa, and apomorphine subcutaneous pump. Physiotherapy is also frequently used.

2.1.2 Germany

2.1.2.1 Characteristics of patients

Numbers of PwP, distribution Male/Female, age distribution and other demographics

There are up to 400,000 patients in Germany. PD in Germany is slightly more common in males (50.8%) than in females. As the incidence of PD increases with age, the prevalence of PD is below 1% in those aged 60 or below and over 3% in those aged 75 or above (Heinzel et al., 2018; Timpel et al., 2020).

Where do they live?

There is no data regarding whether PD patients are distributed in rural areas or in cities.

Education level

No specific data on the educational level of German PD patients exists, and education level is not known as a risk factor for developing PD. However, it could be a risk factor for more rapid cognitive decline (Kierzyńska et al., 2011).

Technological abilities

There is little known about PD patients' technological abilities among German patients. One study using the eHealth literacy scale (EHEALS), found an average score of 23 of perceived users' skills (Bendig et al., 2022), however, these patients volunteered to participate in a telemedicine study so they might not constitute a representative sample.

2.1.2.2 Characteristics of the healthcare system

How is care for PD delivered?

PD patients are principally followed by neurologists (both community-based neurologists and hospital-based ones). In the study by Timpel et al. (2020), mainly elderly and patients with more severe impairment, e.g., in nursing homes, did not see a neurologist for a year.

How is care for PD funded?

Healthcare for PD are mostly funded by public insurance companies.

What does the journey to a PD diagnosis look like in Germany?

Most frequently, a primary care physician suspects PD and refers the patient to a neurologist. Sometimes, patients suspect the disease and ask their primary care physician to refer them to a neurologist. For public insurances, all referrals to neurologists (private practice and hospital) are from primary care physicians ("Hausarzt").

What does the standard practice for PD care look like?

PD patients visit a neurologist every three months. Patients who live in the vicinity of a specialised PD centre (e.g. a university hospital) visit at least once a year. Most PwP are seen

in the outpatient clinics. The most common reasons for patients to be referred are to receive either a second opinion or an advanced therapy for PD. PD nurses are only available in specialised hospital settings or in care research projects. Care networks (parkinsonnetze-deutschland.de) are being built to coordinate interdisciplinary care across disciplines and sectors, however these networks are currently not receiving enough funding.

Available treatments

All oral/transdermal treatments, including Safinamide, Opicapone and Rivastigmine, as well as all advanced treatments (deep brain stimulation, Gamma-Knife, apo pump, LCIG, Levodopa-entacapone-carbidopa intestinal gel (LECIG), subcutaneous levodopa pump (scLEV), and MRgFUS are available.

Most common treatments

The most common pharmacological treatments are oral levodopa, dopamine agonists, COMT inhibitors, safinamide, amantadine, and pumps (all pumps are available). Physiotherapy is often used as well; several PD patients have two physiotherapy sessions per week. Ergotherapy and logotherapy are also used.

2.1.3 Spain

2.1.3.1 Characteristics of patients

Numbers of PwP, distribution Male/Female, age distribution and other demographics

The incidence rate (per 100,000 person-years) in the population aged 65 to 85 and over years is 186.8 for PD. Incidence rates increased with age in men but decreased beyond the age of 79 in women. Age-adjusted relative risk in men compared with women is 2.55 (95% CI) for PD (Benito-León J et al., 2004). The age and sex distribution are 62.6 ± 8.9 years old and 60.3% males, respectively, based on the COPPADIS study (Santos-García D et al., 2015).

Where do they live?

No specific data are available regarding whether PD patients live in rural areas or in cities. Most patients seek care in city hospitals, but come from rural and city areas.

Education levels

There are no specific data regarding the education levels of PD patients in Spain.

Technological abilities

There are no specific data on the technological abilities of Spanish PD patients; however, based on experience, technology literacy mostly depends on the educational level and age more than the condition.

2.1.3.2 Characteristics of the healthcare system

The Spanish Healthcare system is based on universal public healthcare for all.

How is care for PD delivered?

Generally, patients with early-stage PD showing good progress and without complications are treated by a general neurologist with visits every six to nine months. In certain provinces in the South of Spain, where the number of neurologists is scarce, some patients are followed by internists before reaching a neurologist in later stages. Geriatricians handle some older patients. Experts in movement disorders typically handle more complex cases in advanced stages, those with a poorer prognosis from the outset, or atypical cases (such as very young patients or genetic cases). The Spanish Neurology Society has 3,500 members. The Movement Disorders Group has 400 members, mostly neurologists and some specialized nurses and physiotherapists.

How is care for PD funded?

In general, the public health system covers all necessary resources. Private healthcare is an optional resource.

What does the journey to a PD diagnosis look like in Spain?

In general, it is straightforward with accessibility. Patients seek help from the family practitioner, who sends them to the neurologist if they suspect PD. Many times, patients see traumatologists, rheumatologists, and rehabilitation doctors before reaching the neurologist. Waiting lists in the healthcare system for an initial visit to a neurologist are usually around two to three months in the northern half of the country and four to six months in the southern provinces (Andalucia, Extremadura, Murcia). Follow-up appointments typically occur every six to nine months.

What does the standard practice for PD care look like?

Care depends on how stable the patient is and the stage of the disease. Generally, if everything is going well, patients usually have two visits per year. If there are many complications, they may have three or four visits yearly. Based on clinical practice and interviews between colleagues, clinicians working in the public sector have time to receive calls and emails from patients regarding changes in health status, although such direct contact is generally not possible within the public sector.

Which treatments for PD are available?

All approved treatments for PD are available and covered by the national healthcare system. Oral, transdermal, or inhaled treatments, as well as botox therapy. Advanced therapies such as continuous subcutaneous apomorphine infusions or enteral duodopa and, recently, subcutaneous levodopa, inhaled levodopa and sublingual apomorphine are also available. PD surgery with DBS is available in most large reference centers, and high-intensity focused ultrasound (HIFU) is available in five public and four private centers.

Which treatments for PD are most common?

In terms of usage, the most common medications include levodopa, rasagiline, dopaminergic agonists, and, in stages with fluctuations, safinamide, opicapone, or the subcutaneous apomorphine pump.

2.1.4 United Kingdom (UK)**2.1.4.1 Characteristics of patients****Numbers of PwP, distribution Male/Female, age distribution and other demographics**

A Parkinson's UK report of the Clinical Practice Research Datalink (CPRD) using primary care data from 2015 (Parkinson's UK, 2018) found that about 137,000 people were living with PD in the UK. The prevalence rate was 286.5 per 100,000 person-years. The incidence rate was 33.4 per 100,000 person-years, and each year there are about 17,300 new diagnoses of Parkinson's disease in people aged 45 years and above. The prevalence of PD increases with age, i.e., 4-5 per 100,000 people in people aged 30-39 years, compared to 1,696 per 100,000 people aged 80-84 years (equivalent to 1.7% of this age group). Prevalence rates almost double every five-year interval between 50-69 years for both men and women. The prevalence is higher in men than in women; prevalence rates for men aged 50-89 years were more than 1.5 times higher than rates for women in the same age group. This equates to 22 in every 10,000 women and 32 in every 10,000 men diagnosed with Parkinson's disease. By 2025, due to population growth and an increasingly ageing population, the estimated prevalence of Parkinson's disease is expected to increase by 23.2%, and the estimated yearly incidence is expected to increase by 23.9%.

Where do they live?

Urban and non-urban areas.

Education levels

Specific data on educational level of PD patients including immigrants in UK are limited. More than 60% of the population is educated up to university level, 30% to high school and for the 10% of population it is unclear.

Technological abilities

A national audit performed by Parkinson's in UK resulted in that 40 national health parkinson's service had suggested that PD patients are user friendly of any technology which helps them to do day to day activities such as applications, tele-visits/telemedicine, including virtual video consultaion, and wearable sensors. They are very much compatible and adoptable with technology specifically AI and digital instruments.

2.1.4.2 Characteristics of the healthcare system

How is care for PD delivered?

PwPs receive the best care within specialist clinical settings or movement disorder clinics. In the specialist clinic setting, there is an integrated approach when sharing best practice among different HCPs. A multidisciplinary team (MDT) consisting of different HCPs depending on clinic (neurologist, PD nurse specialist, physiotherapist, occupational therapist, speech and language therapist, dietitian) (Skelly R et al., 2012) are part of the integrated approach.

How is care for PD funded?

Care is funded by the National Health Service (NHS), but contribution of pharma to research protocols is also allowed and frequently used. People living with brain and nerve conditions like Parkinson's could benefit from quicker diagnosis and better coordinated care as part of a new NHS initiative, which is also set to free up millions of pounds to reinvest in patient care (NHS England, 2019).

What does the journey to a PD diagnosis look like in the UK?

PD should only be diagnosed after a consultation with a specialist by referral from a primary care physician. Patients normally are referred to secondary care to see a movement disorder specialist, but this is subject to catchment area and location. A PD specialist will conduct a detailed medical history taking and examination to either rule out or confirm PD.

What does the standard practice for PD care look like?

The standard practice for PD care is three to four visits per year, including one in tertiary hospital. PD patients have access to PD nurses and educational therapies including multidisciplinary teams (mainly in university hospitals).

Which treatments for PD are available?

Available treatments include supportive therapies, such as physiotherapy, occupational therapy, speech and language therapy. Also all oral/transdermal treatments (with the exception of Safinamide, Opicapone and Rivastigmine, that is available but not reimbursed) and all advanced treatments (DBS, Gamma-Knife, apo pump and LCIG), with the exception of MRgFUS are available. Subcutaneous levodopa will be available at the end of 2024.

Which treatments for PD are most common?

The most common pharmacological treatments are oral dopamine agonists, levodopa, and apomorphine subcutaneous pump. Physiotherapist is quite used too.

2.2 Digital health technologies in PD

A narrative review of digital health technologies for PD from a patient perspective emphasises the need for such technologies to be more patient-centric (Riggare et al., 2021). The article discusses the current state and potential of digital health technologies in managing PD. Key points include:

- PwPs, as participants in the study, wish to use digital technologies to manage the complexity of their condition, including symptom tracking (motor and non-motor) in relation to various factors like medication, stress, sleep, and exercise. They seek collaboration with their medical teams and access to information, knowledge, and social support.
- Despite significant potential, current digital health initiatives for PD are not fully aligned with patients' expectations. Many technologies are available only to clinicians, and patients often do not have access to their own data. Examples include the Personal Kinetigraph (PKG) and REM-PARK system (Santiago et al., 2019). The mPower smartphone app and Parkinson@Home are notable projects (Michaud M., 2024), but they have yet to provide tangible results for the larger patient community (Riggare et al., 2021).
- The authors propose that future digital health technologies should be directly accessible to PwP, address both motor and non-motor symptoms, support short-term and long-term management, and facilitate collaboration between patients and medical teams. Importantly, these technologies should provide personalised feedback based on collected data.
- For digital health in PD to reach its full potential, the authors recommend recognising patients' right to access their data, providing personalised feedback, and actively involving patients as equal partners in digital health development.
- The article underscores the gap between current digital health offerings and the actual needs and expectations of PwP, advocating for a more inclusive and patient-focused approach in the development of digital health solutions.

For a complete and updated list of available, certified technologies for PD management, the reader is further referred to Section 3 of deliverable D2.4 "Updated report on domain review and datasets".

2.3 Sex and gender impact in PD

Sex differences, as biological aspects of a human being, have been found in numerous areas pertaining to disease presentation and provision of care. Research has found sex differences in symptoms and treatment complications. More severe and common symptoms for women are restless legs, pain, loss of taste and smell, fatigue, depression, constipation, weight change, and excessive sweating (hyperhidrosis) (Martinez-Martin et al., 2012). Even though PD is 1.5 more common for men (Moisan et al., 2015), women have a more benign phenotype, possibly related to female oestrogens, menopause and fertile life span, and with increased expectance of tremor (67%). Women have a higher risk of treatment-related complications, lower chances of effective treatment (Picillo et al., 2017), and faster disease progression (Dahodwala et al., 2018). There are known sex-related neurological differences in cortical thickness and connectivity in Parkinson's disease, which may have implications for diagnosis and treatment (Yadav et al., 2016). Further, motor symptoms, such as tremor as initial symptom, reduced rigidity, and postural instability emerge later for females (Cerri et al., 2019).

Sex, as well as gender considerations regarding social constructs such as expectations and behaviours stemming from sex differences, also impact the provision of care, when influencing patient-provider communication and non-pharmacological disease management (Göttgens et al., 2020). By using a sex- and gender-informed lens, the patient journey in PD can be improved. Both through research and policy, education and awareness, and in healthcare and support, e.g., by increasing the availability of digital health (Castro-Aldrete et al., 2025). There has been minimal sex and gender consideration in mHealth randomized controlled trials for chronic medical conditions like PD (Wang et al., 2020). Hence, such characteristics are important parameters for predictive models within the project, and future sex differences will be identified to ensure inclusivity.

For the ideation and co-creation process for needs mapping, inclusion of sex and gender-balanced groups has so far been considered when recruiting PwPs, HCPs, and PwoPs for the patient panel (see Section 4), as well as for interviews, workshops, and focus groups. Demographics from collected data will also be considered when analysing the data, with focus on sex and/or gender-shaped characteristics, such as different needs, adherence, relationships, or other relevant behaviours stemming from gender or sex differences.

2.4 AI-PROGNOSIS digital health tools concepts

AI-PROGNOSIS aims to develop an AI-enabled digital health ecosystem to advance PD diagnosis and care. The current concept is that the ecosystem will comprise three tools, the mAI-Health and mAI-Care mobile apps for people without and with PD, respectively, and the mAI-Insights Web app for primary and secondary HCPs. The tools will be powered by the predictive models of PD risk, progression and response to medication that AI-PROGNOSIS aims to develop and allow for collection of data serving as input to those models. Data may include digital biomarkers (dBMs) (estimated from passively captured smartwatch and smartphone sensor data or through active digital tests), user self-reports on symptoms, and clinical/genetic data entered by HCPs. Users of both mAI-Health and mAI-Care apps will have access to tailored educational content regarding PD, in the form of short articles. Specifically:

mAI-Health - Mobile app for persons without PD to track their personalised risk of acquiring the disease

The app will enable users, with the help of their attending physicians, to track their quantitative PD risk, along with explainable insights, estimated by the AI-PROGNOSIS PD risk assessment model based on a relevant user profile, smartphone/watch-tracked dBMs data, and occasional self-reports on relevant risk factors/symptoms.

mAI-Care - Mobile app for PwP to track disease progression and medication efficacy

Through the app, PwP and their carers will be able to track symptoms and treatment effects via the AI-PROGNOSIS smartphone/watch-tracked dBMs data, occasional self-reports on their condition, and clinical data shared by their attending physician.

mAI-Insights - HCPs' clinical platform (Web app) supporting PD screening, patient follow-up, and medication optimisation

The platform is intended for both primary and secondary care HCPs. The platform will allow:

- Non-expert (e.g., general practitioners) and expert HCPs (neurologists, movement disorder specialists) to track and identify persons at risk of PD, with explainable estimations of the PD risk assessment model based on clinical data and data shared by users via mAI-Health (dBMs data and self-reports);

- Expert HCPs to: i) track their patients' status through data shared by patients via mAI-Care (dBM's data and self-reports), ii) view projections of the AI-PROGNOSIS PD progression prediction model based on patients' clinical profile and mAI-Care data, and iii) receive individualised predictions of patients' response to PD-specific medication regimens, via the **AI-assisted Medication Decision support (AIMED) module**, powered by the AI-PROGNOSIS medication response predictive model, in order to choose the optimal treatment plan, together with their patients.

Over the course of the project, the AI-PROGNOSIS toolkit (minimum viable products (MVPs)) will be shaped based on the user needs identified (with the initial ones presented in this report) and feedback received by stakeholders during the user research and co-creation activities of the project, as well as the outcomes of the research and development activities of work package WP3 "Predicting PD risk, progression and medication response", including dBM's and predictive models development, as well as genetic analyses.

3 User research and co-creation methods

3.1 User research

User research is a multifaceted discipline that centres on gaining a profound understanding of user behaviours, needs, and motivations. Gathering user feedback through various methods provides qualitative and quantitative data, informing design improvements and enhancing user experiences. User research is an iterative process that plays a pivotal role in shaping user-centric solutions, ensuring that the end product aligns seamlessly with the expectations and preferences of its intended users. As such, it can significantly overlap with co-creation, and the two approaches are commonly used in parallel (De Sutter et al., 2022).

3.1.1 User research in healthcare app development

User research in the context of creating medical apps involves systematic gathering and insights analysis from potential end users and stakeholders to inform the design and development process, ensuring the resulting application meets the specific needs, preferences, and usability requirements of HCPs and patients. It begins with identifying potential end users and learning about their specific needs regarding the tool at hand (Schnall et al., 2016). The research includes broader needs, which are then translated into user preferences, such as functional requirements and app aesthetics (Mrklas et al., 2020). User research allows the design team to align the app in development with the needs of its future users.

3.1.2 Special considerations for user research in healthcare app development

Neglecting to conduct user research can lead to suboptimal design and usability, which, in turn, leads to poor adherence and discontinued use. Many healthcare apps go unused because they fail to meet the needs of their end users (Schnall et al., 2016), demonstrated by the number of mHealth apps downloaded, yet rarely used (McCurdie et al., 2012). An additional challenge is that users' expectations and their actual needs are not always aligned (Ahmed et al., 2022).

One study identified personal, social, and health factors for users of a healthcare platform for elderly with PD or dementia and found the user research and involvement of end-users in the design to be crucial steps to the development of the platform (Ahmed et al., 2022). However, the study conducted three methods of user research across five European countries and found that the users' needs were highly diverse and complex, making it challenging for the

developers to meet all needs. They highlight the importance of focusing on sub-user groups rather than a one-size-fits-all.

3.1.3 Forms of user research

There are many different forms of user research, all targeted at different objectives. This overview of user research methods focuses on forms of user research particularly relevant to the AI-PROGNOSIS context, and what the main benefits of using these methods might be.

3.1.4 Interviews

One-on-one or group interviews are a valuable method in user research thanks to their ability to elicit rich, contextual information directly from participants. Through interviews it is possible to gain a deeper understanding of individuals' experiences, perspectives, and needs. This qualitative approach allows for a nuanced exploration of the complexities inherent in healthcare and medical research, going beyond quantitative data to capture the subjective aspects of individuals' experiences.

Accordingly, interviews serve as a means to place the individual at the centre of the narrative. Patients, for instance, can share their personal journeys, challenges, and aspirations, providing a more complex view of their experiences. This depth of understanding is crucial for developing patient-centred approaches, interventions, or innovations that truly address the real-world needs and concerns of the people involved.

In the context of co-creation, interviews significantly contribute by fostering a collaborative environment. By engaging in interviews, it is possible to establish a direct line of communication with participants, creating a space for open dialogue. This interactive process facilitates the co-creation of knowledge, where all stakeholders actively contribute to the exploration and understanding of healthcare issues. Through dialogue, it is possible to uncover insights that might not be apparent through other research methods, enriching the research process with diverse perspectives. In the co-creation process, interviews enable the identification of unmet needs and gaps. Participants can express their preferences, concerns, and expectations, offering valuable input for improvements.

The dynamic nature of interviews also allows for flexibility in adapting to the unique circumstances and contexts of participants. It is possible to probe deeper into specific issues, explore unexpected themes, and adapt their questioning based on the responses received. This flexibility enhances the co-creation process by making it possible to follow the conversational threads that lead to meaningful insights and solutions.

3.1.5 Focus groups

Focus groups offer a different, yet complementary, approach to understanding diverse perspectives and generating collective insights. Unlike individual or group interviews, focus groups involve a facilitated discussion among a small group of participants. They use set discussion points to guide a discussion. An additional facilitator may be present to help capture the discussion through notetaking and audio recording. Focus groups strive for diverse participants to reach consensus through discussion rather than homogeneous perspectives. However, it is still common to separate user groups (such as patients from HCPs). This method fosters group dynamics, interaction, and the exchange of ideas, contributing to a collaborative environment that also supports co-creation.

One of the key strengths of focus groups is the synergy created by group interactions. Participants, represent different backgrounds, experiences, and viewpoints, and can build on each other's ideas and provide a multifaceted understanding of the topic under investigation. This collaborative dynamic facilitates the co-creation of knowledge as participants collectively

contribute to the exploration issues, generating a range of perspectives that may not emerge in individual interviews.

Focus groups also serve as a platform for validating and contextualising individual experiences. Participants can relate to and affirm each other's experiences, creating a sense of shared understanding and solidarity. This social validation contributes to the co-creation process by establishing common ground and highlighting shared concerns, needs, or preferences within the group. Furthermore, the group dynamic in focus groups can stimulate idea generation and creativity. Participants can engage in brainstorming and collaborative problem-solving, co-creating innovative solutions or strategies for addressing challenges.

3.1.6 Surveys

Surveys are a widely employed user research method, offering a structured and scalable approach to collecting data from many participants. Surveys provide a systematic way to gather quantitative and qualitative information, making it possible to explore a variety of aspects related to experiences and preferences. Surveys also offer a cost-effective and efficient way to collect data from many participants. This scalability is advantageous, as reaching a diverse and geographically dispersed population can be challenging. The ability to gather data from a broad range of individuals enhances the inclusivity of the co-creation process, ensuring that diverse perspectives are considered. Tailoring survey questions to the goals of the co-creation process ensures that the collected data directly informs the development of products or services that align with the needs and expectations of the target population.

Surveys are often designed, disseminated and analysed online. Using Web-surveys, boosts one of the primary advantages of surveys, i.e., their ability to reach a broad and diverse audience. By distributing surveys to many participants, it is possible to gather insights from individuals with varying backgrounds and perspectives. This inclusivity supports the user research process by ensuring a representative sample. This makes Web-surveys an important complement to interviews and focus groups, which will be methods targeted at smaller, select groups.

Moreover, Web-surveys can be administered anonymously, encouraging participants to share their opinions and experiences more freely. This anonymity is especially relevant in healthcare contexts where sensitive topics are explored. Participants may feel more comfortable providing honest feedback, leading to more candid and authentic responses that contribute to a more accurate representation of their views. A commonly adopted format is using Likert-items for informants to evaluate. There are some standardised questions that can aid in survey creation for user needs research which are specific to PD and/or mHealth, such as the Parkinson's Disease Questions (PDQ-8) (Jenkinson et al., 1997) and the e-Health Literacy scale (Norman & Skinner, 2006),

3.2 Co-creation

Co-creation is a participatory approach that involves collaborative efforts between various stakeholders. Through co-creation, diverse perspectives come together to contribute to ideation, problem-solving, and decision-making. By involving users and other stakeholders in the creative process, co-creation not only ensures that the final output meets their needs and expectations, but also cultivates a sense of empowerment and engagement, leading to innovative and user-centric outcomes.

Several terms have emerged from different fields to convey the concept of including key stakeholders in a development process of some sort though in various context. Namely, co-

design, co-production, and co-creation are often confused or used interchangeably, and recent efforts have been made to distinguish between these terms. Co-creation is the most inclusive in terms of being consumer and experience centric whereas co-design is consumer centric and co-production is company centric (Vargas et al., 2022). Additionally, co-creation is aimed at engaging diverse stakeholder experiences rather than selecting specific stakeholders for a specific purpose, and with the aim of understanding complex problems and designing contextually relevant solutions (Vargas et al., 2022). Therefore, co-creation is considered the overarching approach, or an umbrella term for co-design and co-production. Co-creation entails involving stakeholders at as early a stage as possible, ideally before the problem is even clearly defined, whereas co-production involves stakeholders after there is a clear problem on the table (Vargas et al., 2022).

3.2.1 Co-creation in healthcare app development

Research has demonstrated the benefit of co-creation in the development of medical and health technologies, as it allows end users, such as patients and healthcare providers, to actively participate in the design process. This leads to the development of technologies that better meet their needs and preferences, resulting in improved usability and user satisfaction (Børve et al., 2019). User research is a crucial first step, but co-creation enables constant user feedback iteratively throughout the design and development of the app.

One study which employed a co-design approach to an mHealth app, found key differences in their user research between the patient, physician, and researcher preferences. They conclude that through an iterative process of consulting users and negotiating at every step of development, it was possible to reach a consensus on the core app functional requirements while still preserving the diversity of user perspectives (Mrklas et al., 2020).

3.2.2 Special considerations for co-creation in healthcare app development

As mentioned above, when employing a co-creation approach, including diverse stakeholders and engaging various perspectives is inherent, although this of course creates challenges for tool development. Mrklas et al. (2020) described having to negotiate with all user groups (patients, physicians, and researchers) at every step of the design process, as they showed distinctly differing preferences what app functional requirements were important, desirable, convenient, and actionable. Additionally, it was described that even though there were three distinct thought patterns separating the groups, the patients and physicians were still heterogeneous in their preferences (Mrklas et al., 2020). Research exploring user needs in persons with dementia have found that their needs regarding assistive technologies are diverse and possibly in conflict with the needs of their ICGs and HCPs (Ahmed et al., 2022; Meiland et al., 2017).

Another challenge in identifying and negotiating key tool features is that users' expectations do not always meet their actual needs, as found in another study on people with dementia (Guisado-Fernández et al., 2019). This highlights the importance of in-depth exploration of user needs and including multiple stakeholders. In PD, as clinical symptoms fluctuate daily, user needs may also change, requiring again, in-depth exploration of individual needs and the co-creation of a personalized tool (Ahmed et al., 2020).

A technical challenge identified when co-designing with PwP and persons with dementia was the need for educating the users (including HCPs) on the prototype to allow adequate engagement and user feedback (Ahmed et al., 2020).

3.2.3 Forms of co-creation

There are many different forms of co-creation, all targeted at different objectives. This overview of user research methods will focus on forms of co-creation particularly relevant to the AI-PROGNOSIS context, and what the main benefits of using these methods might be.

3.2.4 Workshops

Workshops, both digital and in-person, are commonly used to facilitate a hands-on environment for engaging stakeholders. Discussion topics are prepared ahead, and small group discussions and activities are held with a facilitator. There are numerous examples of workshop use in co-creating mHealth tools (Lundell et al., 2022 & Dugstad et al., 2019). One of the primary strengths of workshops in co-creation is their ability to bring together various stakeholders. By assembling a diverse group with different perspectives and expertise, workshops create a space for cross-disciplinary collaboration. This interdisciplinary approach is crucial for co-creating holistic solutions that consider complex dimensions. Workshops also facilitate active participation and engagement among participants. Through structured activities, individuals can contribute their unique insights and experiences. This collaborative energy fosters a sense of ownership and involvement in the co-creation process, empowering participants to play an active role in shaping a project. Furthermore, workshops provide a platform for immediate feedback and iteration. Participants can share their thoughts in real-time, allowing for adjustments and refinements during the co-creation process. This iterative nature ensures that the resulting solutions are responsive to the input and preferences of the participants, contributing to the development of more user-centric and effective interventions.

3.2.5 Brainstorming sessions

Brainstorming sessions are creative and focused co-creation activities designed to generate a wide array of ideas and solutions to address specific challenges. These sessions encourage participants to think innovatively, leveraging the collective intelligence of diverse stakeholders to explore new perspectives, interventions, and approaches to various issues. One of the primary advantages of brainstorming sessions in co-creation is their ability to inspire creativity and idea generation. Participants are encouraged to freely express their thoughts, share insights, and propose innovative solutions. Brainstorming sessions are not only about generating ideas but also about prioritising and selecting the most promising concepts. Through facilitated discussions and group evaluations, participants can collectively identify key priorities and focus areas. This collaborative decision-making process ensures that the co-creation effort is guided by the most impactful and feasible ideas (Bonnardel & Didier, 2020).

3.2.6 Card sorting

Card sorting provides a structured approach for participants to categorise and organise information or concepts. This method involves the use of physical or digital cards representing different elements, allowing participants to group and prioritise these elements according to their own mental models. Card sorting is particularly useful for information architecture, content organisation, and understanding user preferences. It allows for the identification of common patterns and consensus among participants. The method helps with identifying recurring themes, shared preferences, and areas of agreement. This consensus-building aspect is valuable for making informed decisions in the co-creation process, ensuring that the final product reflects the collective input of the participants (Tankala & Sherwin, 2024).

3.3 Use of personas

A user persona, often referred to simply as a persona, is a detailed and fictional representation of a hypothetical user or customer for a product, service, or system. Personas are a

fundamental tool in UI/UX design and product development, helping teams better understand the needs and expectations of their target audience – as well as empathise with them. These representations provide a clear and human-centric reference for design and decision-making. By designing for specific personas, teams can create more user-centric solutions that are more likely to meet user requirements and deliver a better user experience. It is essential to create multiple personas if the intended product or service caters to a diverse user base, as each persona will have different needs and characteristics.

3.3.1 Key characteristics of personas

Key aspects of a user persona include, but are not limited to:

- **Name and demographics**
The persona is given a name and basic demographic information is specified, such as age, gender, location, education, and job title. This helps create a relatable character. It is also helpful to add a photo for stakeholders who are more visually oriented.
- **Background and biography**
A backstory should be provided for the persona, including their job history, family life, hobbies, and other relevant personal details. This adds depth to the persona, and contextual depth is helpful when deploying persona-based activities.
- **Goals and objectives**
The persona's primary goals, needs, and objectives should be outlined. What are they trying to accomplish when using the product or service?
- **Challenges and pain points**
The persona's pain points, obstacles, and challenges that they may face when trying to achieve their goals should be identified. This helps in the creation of complex user scenarios using personas.
- **Motivations and values**
The persona's motivations, values, and what drives their decision-making should be explored. What are their priorities and preferences? This helps guide behaviour and assist with analyses of use patterns.
- **Behaviour and habits**
The persona's typical behaviour should be described, including how they might interact with technology, their daily routines, and habits related to the product or service that is being evaluated.
- **Tech savviness**
The persona's level of familiarity and comfort with technology and the digital world should be outlined, as this significantly impacts their user experience.
- **Communication preferences**
It can sometimes help to specify how the persona prefers to communicate and what channels they use (e-mail, social media, phone calls).
- **Further customisation**
It is possible to include quotes, anecdotes, preferences and similar from actual or potential stakeholders to make the persona feel more authentic and relatable.

3.3.2 Developing personas further

There are several different methods for further developing personas. Two particularly relevant tools to this context are empathy maps and user journey maps, described below.

3.3.2.1 Empathy maps

An empathy map is a visual tool or framework used in design thinking and UI/UX design to help teams better understand and empathise with their target users or customers (Experience, World Leaders in Research-Based User). It is a collaborative exercise that allows designers, researchers, and other team members to gain insights into the thoughts, feelings, needs, and behaviours of the people they are designing for. Empathy maps are particularly useful for building a deeper understanding of user personas and improving the user experience of products, services, or solutions.

An empathy map typically consists of four quadrants, each focused on different aspects of the user's experience, or what they say, think, feel, or do.

- **Saying**

In this quadrant, the explicit statements, phrases, and quotes that represent what the user says are captured, such as their goals, pain points, or specific needs. This information is often gathered from user interviews or surveys.

- **Thinking**

In this quadrant, the user's inner thoughts and considerations are in focus. What might the user be thinking but not explicitly expressing? What are their concerns, hopes, and aspirations?

- **Feeling**

This quadrant is dedicated to the user's emotions and feelings. What are the user's emotional reactions and experiences related to the product or service? How do they feel about specific aspects of their interaction with it?

- **Doing**

Here, the user's actions and behaviours are documented. What actions or behaviours does the user engage in as they interact with the product or service? This can include their physical actions, such as clicking buttons, as well as broader behavioural patterns.

Empathy maps can be generated either through direct input from relevant stakeholders or from information gathered from user research, interviews, observations, or surveys.

3.3.2.2 User journey maps

A user journey map is a visualisation or narrative representation of the steps and interactions a user goes through when they engage with a product, service, or system. It is a way to map out the user's various touchpoints and experiences, from their initial contact with the product or service to their eventual goal or outcome.

The goal for user journeys is to serve as a valuable tool for understanding the user's perspective and guide the design to create more user-centric and effective solutions. They are commonly used in UI/UX design to better understand and design for the user's experience.

Using an existing persona, a user journey is undertaken, which can both help strengthen the persona (what information about the persona is missing in order to understand what path they would choose in a specific process) and improve the service or product in question.

- **Touchpoints**

Focuses on identifying the various points of interaction the user has with the product or service.

- **Steps**

Outlines the specific steps or actions the user takes during their journey. This could be a linear progression or a more complex, non-linear path depending on the complexity of the user's interactions.

- **Emotions and motivations**

Documents the user's emotional state and motivations at each step of the journey. This helps in understanding how users feel and what drives their decisions.

- **Barriers and pain points**

Highlights any obstacles, challenges, or pain points the user encounters during their journey. These can be areas for improvement in the user experience.

- **Goals and outcomes**

Specifies the user's goals or desired outcomes. This could be logging an activity, getting information, or achieving some other objective.

- **Channels and devices**

Indicates the devices and channels (e.g., mobile, desktop, in-person, social media) the user may use during their journey.

- **Opportunities for improvement**

The user journey can be used to identify areas where the user experience can be enhanced and where the product or service can better meet the user's needs and expectations.

User journeys can be generated either through direct input from relevant stakeholders or from information gathered from user research, interviews, observations, or surveys.

3.4 Stakeholder engagement, follow-up, and adherence (the Samka framework)

The Samka framework is an approach to collaboration in medical research and healthcare that was developed in 2022 (Clareborn et al., 2023). It is based on an extensive review of scientific literature and reports, a series of interviews with patient and next-of-kin representatives, intra-organisational case studies, and several years of dialogue focusing on needs and challenges. A report on this approach was published in 2022 and revised in 2023. The report addresses different approaches to collaboration between different stakeholder groups, such as co-creation. It outlines six main recommendations, or principles, that are vital to successful co-creation. See also below and the checklist in Appendix II.

Principle 1 Define clear aims, objectives, and evaluation criteria – together

Co-create *with* patients, next of kin, and other end users rather than *for* them. Define common goals early on and establish a process for evaluation and follow-up.

Principle 2 Confront power imbalances

Good collaboration is based on a balance of competencies that complement each other. Discuss early on which perspectives are valued and how they are valued. Be open to the fact that some or all of the parties involved might have a need for skills development.

Principle 3 Communicate to build trust and confidence

Clear and transparent communication is an essential component of collaboration. Reflect on the purpose of the communication and how it can be adapted to the wishes and needs of different stakeholders.

Principle 4 Create conditions for remuneration and representativity

A remuneration model must be in place and agreed upon before any cooperation is initiated. It is also important to create conditions enabling the right level of representativity for the collaborative initiative in question.

Principle 5 Build a long-term structure for collaboration

Short-termism makes successful collaboration impossible. A long-term and flexible structure for collaboration, for example in the form of processes, IT systems, allocated working time, budget, management systems and adapted leadership, is necessary for sustainable collaborative work.

Principle 6 Share positive and negative experiences and learn from others

Create conditions for continuous learning and for lessons to be passed on beyond the partners. Avoid reinventing the wheel by learning from the experiences of others and using existing knowledge resources.

A description of the way these principles will be adopted in AI-PROGNOSIS can be found in Section 4.4.

4 User research and co-creation in AI-PROGNOSIS

The AI-PROGNOSIS approach regarding user research and co-creation is described in this section. The stakeholders described here are those who will be involved in the user research and co-creation process of AI-PROGNOSIS. To adhere to the co-creation process, a patient panel was involved in the project in order to reach the needs of PwP as stakeholders. Further, a framework was used to ensure that all stakeholders share the same goals and priorities.

4.1 Ethical Approvals and GDPR

Ethical approval by the Swedish Ethical Review Authority was needed to allow AI-PROGNOSIS partner UU, leading Task 2.2 on user research and co-creation, to establish the patient panel (see also Section 4.3). The application was submitted in month (M) 3 of the project (September 2023) and approval was given in M6 (December 2023, Dnr 2023-05949-01) for “User perspectives and co-creation for EU project AI-PROGNOSIOS”. This is the reason why user research activities involving the patient panel were initiated at the beginning of 2024 and not in the first semester of the project (July – December 2023) as initially planned.

An ethical application was also submitted for collecting data from the user need-survey in 2024, “User needs and perspectives for EU project AI-PROGNOSIS”. This was exempted from ethical review according to the Swedish Ethical Review Authority, with decision number 2024-05505-01. In Spain, the clinical partner FIN, through their clinical site Hospital Ruber Internacional in Madrid, also needed to establish an ethical approval to be able to collect survey data from HCPs. The application was named “AI-PROGNOSIS: AI-based assessment of risk and prognosis in Parkinson’s disease – a subproject: AI-PROGNOSIS online survey” and was approved 6/12/2024 by the Research Ethics Committee of Hospital Ruber Internacional in Madrid.

For all collected data from stakeholders, we have followed the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to protect all participants’ personal data and privacy⁴. Personal data collected for PwP and HCPs was name, age, profession, years with PD, sex, and geographic (country living in right now). When sensitive personal data was included, such as health, we applied for ethical approval for that country and organization that would collect and store the

⁴ [General Data Protection Regulation \(GDPR\) – Legal Text](#)

data. No other sensitive data were collected for the user research and co-creation within the project. Other data collected concerns opinions of AI, disease prediction and progression, PD management, and other technical aspects of the applications.

The data collected are processed by consortium partners under a joint controllership arrangement, as defined in Article 26 GDPR. Roles and responsibilities for compliance, including legal bases, data subject rights and technical safeguards, have been formally documented in a Data Processing Agreement.

All participants have consent to their data being collected and stored, by receiving written information about the purpose of the interviews, focus groups, surveys, and workshops, and after that consent through video-recordings or by ticking an approval box for the surveys. These consent procedures are aligned with Articles 7 and 13 of the GDPR, ensuring that consent is freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous and that participants are fully informed of their rights, including access, erasure and withdrawal.

Sensitive data collected are being stored by UU and is protected by appropriate technical and organizational measures, where only authorized persons have access to the data. For technical measures the data are stored in secure servers within a specially protected IT environment, and the data are backed up. Access to identifiable data is strictly limited to partners involved in the original data collection and only within the premises where informed consent was obtained, in accordance with Article 32 GDPR.

The rest of the data are being stored at the Sharepoint/Teams account of AI-PROGNOSIS, with access to the project partners. The survey data are stored at the online survey-management platform EUSurvey⁵ during the data collection period. All participants can request deletion of data, except data collected by surveys, since that data are anonymous and cannot be traced back to the participant. All data are stored and processed for as long as it is necessary to ensure the quality of the research being performed within AI-PROGNOSIS.

After the end of the project, data that are no longer necessary will either be anonymized for continued scientific use or securely deleted, unless legal grounds exist for its further retention, pursuant to Articles 6 or 9 GDPR.

4.2 Stakeholders for user research and co-creation

Partner stakeholders for user research and co-creation are defined as:

- Clinical partners
- User-oriented partners
- Technical partners
- Bioethics partner

Non-partner stakeholders for user research and co-creation are defined as:

- Persons with PD
- Persons without PD
- Carers
- Relevant HCPs

Technical, user-oriented, and bioethics partners are only involved in user research and co-creation as enablers or facilitators. The other stakeholders are listed in **Figure 1**. The context

⁵ EUSurvey - <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/welcome>

where the various stakeholder groups are most likely to contribute is also included, as well as a mapping of the stakeholder groups to project activities.

Figure 1 Overview of AI-PROGNOSIS user characteristics.

4.3 Patient panel

To fulfil the AI-PROGNOSIS objective for co-creation and effectively engaging key stakeholders in the design and development of the AI-PROGNOSIS tools, a patient panel was established under the initiative of partner UU. To establish the panel, an ethics approval application was submitted to the Swedish Ethical Review Authority in month 3 (M3), and approval was granted in M6 when the recruitment of members started. Panel members were recruited using purposive and snowball sampling with an email from a project member who has contact with many patient organisations as a PwP herself. The criteria were that panel members have a PD diagnosis, live in one of the six countries of interest (France, Germany, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, the UK), know sufficient English to participate, and have a base understanding of AI/eHealth to follow the discussions. The sampling aimed at recruiting an equal spread across the six participating countries while achieving diversity in other areas, including employment status, level of knowledge of AI and PD, diagnosis and treatment experiences, causes of PD (e.g., genetic), previous research participation, age, and sex.

Those who responded to the email with interest were sent textual information and either invited to an information session or provided the recording of an information session, with the opportunity to ask questions and think about it. Once a participant agreed to participate, informed consent was obtained and recorded verbally, and an onboarding interview was conducted on the Zoom platform (zoom.us). The interviews included background on each member's diagnosis journey, opinions on AI in health care generally, and expectations, hopes, and concerns for the project. There are 13 (four women, nine men) active members of the patient panel, with an average age of 52 years and a standard deviation (SD) of 10.12 years, and an average of 9 years since diagnosis with a SD of 4.57 years. The participants reside in six countries: France (n=2), Germany (n=3), Portugal (n=3), Spain (n=1), Sweden (n=2), and UK (n=3). Their professional backgrounds cover a range of fields, including MD, IT, security, pharmacist, artist/crafter, and teacher.

4.4 Stakeholder engagement in AI-PROGNOSIS

The Samka framework (see Section 3.4), and its principles are integrated into AI-PROGNOSIS to ensure that representativity and democratic principles guide the user research and co-

creation processes. As well as that all stakeholders share the same outlook on goals and priorities. Each of the six principles (see **Table 1**) are given specific attention. Using the principles as a common point of departure is helpful in guiding shared decision-making and co-creation activities in a way that ensures that all stakeholders are involved at the earliest possible stage. Special attention will be given on clarifying beforehand the impact of patient's input regarding decision-making.

Table 1 The Samka principles and how they are integrated in AI-PROGNOSIS

Principle 1 - Define clear aims, objectives and evaluation criteria
To ensure adherence to this objective, the aim is to clarify this ahead of planned co-activities. For instance, this has been done by informing the participants of the purpose of the co-activity, the next steps, how they as participants will get feedback on their input, and clarified how their input will be used. This has been done in writing (a participation information letter) as well as on a continuous basis verbally.
Principle 2 - Confront power imbalances
The consortium uses the co-creation principles as a common point of departure to serve as a continuous reminder of power imbalances between stakeholders. Special care has been given to addressing power imbalances in mixed co-creation sessions, such as workshops with many different stakeholders. One important aspect has been clearly stating everyone's role and expertise and understanding their expectations of the project. For instance, this has been done by informing all participants ahead of the co-activity regarding which stakeholder groups will be represented and what their roles will be. Also, collecting their expectations by asking them orally or in writing and trying to meet them throughout the whole project.
Principle 3 - Communicate to build trust and confidence
Within a project's integrated communication strategy, focus is on stakeholder inclusivity and openness, which has helped ensure adherence, trust-building, and confidence. For instance, the actions taken in support of principles 1 and 2 above are relevant here, in addition to keeping stakeholders in the loop regarding new developments in the project as an iterative process of the users' needs.
Principle 4 - Create conditions for remuneration and representativity
Within a project, funds for remuneration of participation need to be secured. Representativity, such as professional backgrounds, different knowledge of the intended development/intervention, diversity of symptoms and treatments as patients, country, age, sex and gender, has been an important focus in the consolidation of participation and will continue to be considered throughout the project.
Principle 5 - Build a long-term structure for collaboration
It is important to continuously address the future of the ecosystem and to what extent stakeholder input will be made feasible in the long term. This is an iterative process throughout the whole project to ensure and build trust and lay a foundation for further collaboration. In this process, we attempt to meet the needs and expectations of the participants, as well as show how their input affects the progression of the project. This has thus far been done through a good communication strategy (see principle 3) and recurring meetings with participants to ensure that the projects and development meet their needs. This has aided the continued collaboration with participants since they realize that their input is relevant to the project and to other contexts in which it functions.
Principle 6 - Share positive and negative experiences and learn from others
This principle ensures openness, visibility, and reuse of project approaches and outcomes through open science, effective dissemination/communication, and strategic networking/joint activities. Positive and negative experiences in user research and co-creation activities will be shared and discussed in various contexts per the project's dissemination strategy. An example of how co-creation experiences have been disseminated thus far is through a conference paper (Luckhaus et al., 2025).

In terms of networking and joint initiatives, as described in Principle 6, UU collaborates with the European Patient Involvement organization (EUPATI) and several other PwP stakeholder initiatives and regularly contributes to related networking activities. Other networking initiatives have also started within the project and are reported in deliverable D6.3 “First report on project visibility and educational material”, as well as will be reported in deliverable D6.6 “Final report on project visibility and educational material”.

4.5 User research

User research is a central part of AI-PROGNOSIS and lays the foundation for an agile process that has involved PwP, PwoP, HCPs, and other relevant stakeholders (e.g. informal caregivers) in the design, development, and testing of the AI-PROGNOSIS tools. An overview of the user research flow is depicted in **Figure 2**. Secondary research of existing evidence (see Section 5.1) that is relevant to the tools the project aims to develop will create the primary hypotheses and assumptions around the behaviour and needs of key stakeholders, as well as current solutions utilised and the standard clinical practice. Primary user research has followed. Generative semi-structured interviews with clinicians and need-identification focus groups with PwP, PwoP, carers, HCPs, and healthcare enablers, together with clinical, technical, and bioethics AI-PROGNOSIS teams, have given more detailed insights on the current clinical standard on PD screening, prognosis, and care, and enabled the discovery of users’ motivations and needs. Interviews and focus groups have been organised by patient-research partner UU, with the help of clinical partners (CHUT, KCL, TUD, FIN), and they have been facilitated by UU and technical partner AUTH (see Sections 5.2 and 5.2.3). Feedback from interviews and focus groups have been analysed and interpreted to inform the final round of hypotheses and assumptions that will be validated against a greater population with web surveys for general value assessment and prioritisation.

Outputs of this foundational user research process have yielded the core set of user needs and user stories that have shaped the product backlog, guided research and development (R&D), and assessed sex/gender impact across all project processes and products. User research has been performed iteratively during the whole development process, beyond initial needs identification, as prototypes are being tested for usability, effectiveness, and user satisfaction, but will be then encompassed in the co-creation process (see next section).

Figure 2 User research in AI-PROGNOSIS

4.6 Co-creation

In AI-PROGNOSIS, stakeholders, as defined in Section 4.2, have iteratively collaborated in the design of the AI-PROGNOSIS tools in a way that is meaningful, relevant, and satisfies users, industry, and societal needs. An agile methodology has been followed with three rounds of strategic co-creation workshops (**Figure 3**). The procedure of co-creation workshops is based on four distinguished phases of design thinking: exploration, ideation, prototyping, and reflection. During the exploration phase, participants introduced themselves and were presented the main scope of the workshops, setting the objectives for the next phase. The ideation phase included moderated discussions and activities where participants responded

to the issues presented, share personal insights, and brainstormed both altogether and in subgroups. During prototyping, storyboards of the selected ideas were created, focusing on user journeys and value propositions of the proposed features for each AI-PROGNOSIS tool. The co-creation workshops ended with a reflection from all participants, a decision on the next steps, and a collection of all observations and materials have been analysed and created the basis of the MVPs.

Figure 3 Co-creation of MVPs in AI-PROGNOSIS; PwP and expert patients are now part of the patient panel.

The first round of co-creation workshops focuses on Trustworthy AI design and specifications (see also D2.2 “Trustworthy AI development and evaluation framework (fundamental version)”), with an emphasis on human autonomy, fairness and equality, explainability and transparency, and the ethical and user-driven concerns around the use of AI in healthcare and self-care. The first round of co-creation workshops has been organised and facilitated by UU, technical partners AUTH and AING, and bioethics partner UOXF (see Section 5.3).

Following the first round of co-creation workshops, a series of prototyping development sprints (organised by partner SQD leading software development) has updated the initial product backlog focusing on each one of the tools, based on the feedback collected during user research and the insights of the first co-creation workshops lead to the first product increment with early mock-up prototyping and internal testing (see the timeline in Section 4.8, Table 2).

The second round of co-creation workshops focused on each tool's UI/UX design to explore the importance and granularity of the insights, metrics, and symptom-tracking features, engaging the various target audiences. The second round of co-creation workshops has been organised and facilitated by UU, technical partners (AUTH, AING, KUL, CERTH), and SQD (see Section 5.3).

Another round of prototyping sprints, moderated and unmoderated usability testing with a small pool of participants, have served as an outcome to the alpha version of the tools.

The final round of co-creation workshops focused on hands-on experience and feedback with the tools from all target audiences to identify and refine the features with the highest value and impact potential and set the final technical and product requirements and fixes. The final round of prototyping and testing sprints of the beta versions of the AI-PROGNOSIS tools will produce the initial MVPs. Co-creation workshops have been performed in-person and remotely to further increase accessibility, utilising suitable collaborative tools for brainstorming (Miro, miro.com), interactive mock-ups (Figma, figma.com) and usability testing (UsabilityHub, usabilityhub.com).

4.7 Incorporating feedback to the technical process

All co-creation activities and user research have been conducted together with the technical partners (WP3 'Predicting PD risk, progression and medication response' and WP4 'The AI-PROGNOSIS digital health ecosystem') in the project. They have set the agenda for the activities with either interview questions and protocols (see Appendices), or visualizing screenshots of interfaces of the applications. Being part of the activities have made it possible for them to have a first view and understanding of the participating stakeholders' needs and feedback of the development. The facilitator (UU) of the activities has performed analysis together with the WP4 Leader, SQD, after collecting the data. This has helped us to form a common understanding of updated user needs and requirements.

Further for the updated user needs in this deliverable, there have been systematic integration of stakeholder feedback from the extended user needs-survey into the technical process, with several analysis done (first one in March 2025 and the second one in June 2025) by UU. A second survey with focus on user needs for PwP has been disseminated in April 2025 and is also being valued highly in regard of updating the user needs and requirements.

4.8 Timeline and distribution of stakeholder input

Table 2 includes a timeline of stakeholders' co-creation activities, being further described in Sections 4.5 and 4.6. An overview of the different activities is explained below:

- **Panel consolidation and introduction:** Representatives from the patient panel participated in the introductory activities.
- **Focus group participation:** Representatives from the patient panel participated in the focus groups.
- **AI workshop preparation (prep) and participation:** Representatives from the patient panel and HCPs contributed to the preparations for and participated in the AI workshops.
- **Survey prep:** Representatives from the patient panel and partner HCPs contributed to the preparations of the web surveys.
- **Survey participation:** HCPs, PwP, and PwoP (including people at risk) participated as survey respondents.
- **Persona review:** Representatives from the patient panel and HCPs have participated in continuously reviewing, improving, and adding to the personas used in co-activities.
- **UI/UX workshop prep:** Representatives from the patient panel and HCPs have contributed to the preparations for the UI/UX workshop.
- **UI/UX workshop participation:** Representatives from the patient panel, internal clinical project partners, and external HCPs have participated in the UI/UX workshop.
- **Hands-on experience and feedback workshop participation:** Representatives from the patient panel and HCPs will/have participated in the hands-on experience and feedback workshop.
- **Process evaluation:** All patient panel representatives will be invited to discuss their experiences with and give feedback on the co-activities over the course of the project.

Table 2 Timeline of stakeholders' co-creation activities

Project month	Panel activity	PwP activity	Partner HCP activity	Non-partner HCP activity
M7 (Jan 2024)	Panel consolidation and introduction.			
M8 (Feb 2024)	Focus group participation		Interview participation	Interview participation
M9 (Mar 2024)	AI workshop prep and participation	AI workshop participation	Interview participation	Interview participation
M11 (May 2024)			Survey preparation	
M12 (Jun 2024)	Persona review Survey preparation		Survey preparation	
M13 (Jul 2024)	Persona review		Persona review	
M14 (Aug 2024)	UI/UX workshop preparation		UI/UX workshop preparation	
M15 (Sep 2024)			UI/UX workshop participation	
M16 (Oct 2024)	UI/UX workshop participation Survey preparation pilots		Survey preparation	
M17 (Nov 2024)			Persona review UI/UX workshop participation	UI/UX workshop participation
M18 (Dec 2024)	Survey dissemination & participation	Survey participation	Survey dissemination	Survey participation
M19 (Jan 2025)	Survey dissemination & participation	Survey participation	Survey dissemination UI/UX workshop participation	Survey participation UI/UX workshop participation
M20 (Feb 2025)	Persona review Survey dissemination & participation	Survey participation	Persona review Survey dissemination	Survey participation
M21 (Mar 2025)	Persona review	Survey participation	Persona review	Survey participation

Project month	Panel activity	PwP activity	Partner HCP activity	Non-partner HCP activity
	Survey dissemination & participation		Survey dissemination	
M22 (Apr 2025)	UI/UX workshop participation Hands-on experience and feedback workshop participation Survey dissemination & participation	Survey participation	UI/UX workshop participation Survey (short survey) preparation	Survey participation
M23 (May 2025)	Survey dissemination & participation	Survey participation	Survey dissemination	Survey participation
M24 (Jun 2025)	Hands-on experience and feedback workshop participation	Survey participation	Survey dissemination	Survey participation
M25 (Jul 2025)		Survey participation	Survey dissemination	Survey participation
M26 (Aug 2025)		Survey participation	Hands-on experience and feedback workshop participation Survey dissemination	Hands-on experience and feedback workshop participation Survey participation
M27 (Sep 2025)	Persona review	Survey participation	Persona review	
M28 (Oct 2025)	Project process evaluation			

The above-mentioned activities are further described through the project's key performance indicators (Section 4.9) and co-creation findings (Sections 5.2 & 5.3).

4.9 Key performance indicators of user research and co-creation

The key performance indicators of the AI-PROGNOSIS user research and co-creation activities along with their targets and current values are presented in **Table 3**.

Table 3 User research and co-creation activities key performance indicators (KPIs).

Key performance indicators for user research and co-creation activities	Actual status of the key performance indicators
Key performance indicators for user research and co-creation activities	Actual status of the key performance indicators
1 round of focus groups/surveys	2 rounds of focus groups/surveys
3 rounds of co-creation workshops	3 rounds of co-creation workshops
≥3 prototyping sprints	3 prototyping sprints
≥500 persons with/without PD from ≥4 countries involved across all activities	269 persons with/without PD from 16 countries are involved across all activities
≥50 HCPs from ≥4 countries involved across all activities	84 HCPs from 9 countries involved across all activities

Prototyping sprints refer to software development sprints, at the end of which, testing of product increments with a small number of stakeholders will take place.

5 User research and co-creation findings

In this chapter, secondary research findings from the literature and primary research findings from interviews, focus groups, workshops, and surveys with external and internal HCPs, PwP, PwoP, and the patient panel are presented. Research findings within the project identified that focus was on ethical considerations and privacy concerns for AI monitoring. This goes in line with the initial findings, where concerns were expressed regarding the communication of the risk of acquiring PD through an app, rather than in person from an HCP.

The primary research findings further showed that for mAI-Health app it was important that as much data as possible should be collected automatically, reducing the input need for the users. Also, it was deemed that those at PD risk may need more motivation than those already diagnosed. For mAI-Care app it was considered important with actionable data, either to act upon or to get a deeper learning from. For mAI-Insights risk-, progression-, and medication response reports were discussed. To track progression, it was important to consider daily life activities for PwP and people at risk. Symptom tracking is a most desired AI feature for all user groups.

5.1 Secondary research findings

Most research on AI for early diagnosis and monitoring is focusing on AI-based wearables (Radu Ilesan et al., 2022). However, here we focus on secondary research findings providing for a background on the view of AI as an application (and additionally watch-tracked dBMs data) for tracking persons at risk of acquiring PD, to track disease progression, and as a support for follow-up and medication efficacy.

Plouvier et al (2015) found that PwP divide the diagnostic pathway into three time “intervals”: recognition of the symptoms; the decision to seek help; and the process of diagnosing PD.

Research has identified both potential benefits and ethical challenges for each time interval. It is also described that just over half of the PwP believed that their diagnosis was delayed, although in some cases, due to their own delayed healthcare-seeking choices (Plouvier et al., 2015). Additionally, the majority reported that their GP did not recognise the symptoms, even when the patient suggested PD. However, most participants reported being satisfied with their diagnosis trajectory (Plouvier et al., 2015).

Schaeffer et al (2020) surveyed PwP in which they were asked (retrospectively) if they wished they had been notified of their PD risk prior to diagnosis. They found that PwP saw a benefit to disease detection, as long as the news was delivered appropriately, highlighting the importance of follow-up and agency when giving an early diagnosis of (prodromal) PD. Most of the PwP were sceptical regarding early risk disclosure, especially regarding the lack of pharmacologic options. However, once reminded of the potential ability to mitigate with exercise and diet changes, the percentage who supported early risk disclosure nearly doubled (85%). The informants also expressed the importance of freedom of choice. Schaeffer et al (2020) stressed the need to establish an early diagnosis “culture” within healthcare, including early clarification of the patient’s desire to know as well as implementing regular support and follow-up after risk disclosure.

Kayis et al (2023) investigated the attitudes of neurologists toward risk disclosure in prodromal PD. They found that the majority (77.9%) of the 222 neurologists questioned favoured disclosing the risk of PD among idiopathic REM sleep behavior disorder (iRBD) (polysomnography-confirmed) patients depending on the circumstances - mainly given that the patient provided consent. A small majority reported always or never disclosing PD risk, although the number who initially reported never disclosing risk was reduced by half once they were informed/reminded of the potential protective factor of lifestyle changes in the prodromal stage. These findings along with Schaeffer et al (2020), demonstrate the importance of lifestyle interventions and education. No significant differences were found based on age, sex, gender, academic title, or field of interest.

Paccoud et al (2024) investigated differences in use and opinions on digital medical devices for monitoring PD among PwP in Germany, France, and Spain. Their cross-sectional survey found differences based on age and sociodemographics. Higher education levels were associated with lower trust for AI and data-sharing, though privacy concerns were still low (5%) and respondents were 3-4 times more willing to use if they received clear instruction and feedback (e.g. progress reports). Respondents in Germany reported a higher use (Paccout et al, 2024). Ho et al. (2023) explored ethical consideration of AI monitoring among PwP. The participants expressed ethical concerns as well as potential benefits on individual, interpersonal, professional, and societal levels. Overall, participants expressed potential for more effective and personalised care (both clinical and self-care), as longitudinal monitoring could capture more nuances than a physician does in short and infrequent visits, which is important in a fluctuating disease like PD. Additionally, those who live alone might get a more accurate picture of their condition with the help of AI, as there is no one else to provide such insights (Ho et al., 2023). In another study, PwP recalled that recognizing symptoms (pre-diagnosis) took a while from when they first noticed something was abnormal and that it was friends and family who often first noticed, which led to the decision to seek help. (Plouvier et al, 2015).

Privacy was a top concern for PwP regarding AI monitoring (Ho et al., 2023). For many, it is crucial that nothing more than is needed is monitored. For example, to monitor facial expressions, regular face-to-face camera check-ins suffice, as exemplified by one participant, and having cameras around the home would be too much. All informants stressed the

importance of consent when using AI monitoring and predictive analytics, although many questioned how to ensure informed and voluntary consent, especially with disease progression, which can often cause cognitive decline. Another concern was illness identity, as constant monitoring and use of technology for their disease could serve as a constant reminder that they are “ill.”

5.2 Primary research findings

With focus on user needs, primary research with different methods for data collection has been performed. This has led to initial, and later on, updated user needs, as well as one full paper and one published conference paper. More papers are planned to be submitted using these findings.

5.2.1 Patient panel onboarding interviews

The international patient panel was assembled in late 2023, and onboarding semi-structured interviews were held with 13 out of 14 panel members during January to March 2024. The interviews consisted of four women and nine men representing six countries (France n=2, Germany n=3, Portugal n=3, Spain n=1, Sweden n=1, and UK n=3). The participants have an age range of 40-75 years old (mean age=52) and a range of 1-17 years living with PD (mean years living with PD=9). For a more explicit result, the data from two focus groups with the patient panel (see described in 5.2.2) was also used for this analysis and aim.

The limited knowledge on AI-assisted monitoring from the perspective of PwP has found multi-level ethical concerns for AI prognostics: on personal, interpersonal, professional/institutional, and societal levels (Schaeffer E et al, 2020; Ho A et al, 2023). As AI-use for PD increases, it is essential to explore the ethical dimensions from the users' perspective, including perceptions of benefits, potential harms, privacy risks, and broader concerns. Therefore, the aim here was to explore ethical considerations of using AI in PD management from a PwP perspective.

The interviews and focus groups were analyzed abductively as one dataset, using a simplified version of Thompson's eight-step Abductive Thematic Analysis (Thompson J, 2022). This method of abductive reasoning involves iteratively moving between empirical data and theoretical framework (the bioethics framework) to refine interpretations (Tavory I & Timmermans S, 2014). An inductive coding in Taguette© (taguette.org) was conducted, using “considerations for AI in managing PD” as an initial analytic lens. Codes were low-level descriptors of salient statements emerging from the text. The codes were then transferred into Miro©, a collaborative online “whiteboard”, where codes were inductively grouped into preliminary themes. An overarching ethical dimension emerged, prompting the abductive step of refining the research focus towards ethical considerations, and application of the biomedical ethical principles (Beauchamp T & Childress J, 2019) to deductively categorize the codes/preliminary themes. The results are presented according to the biomedical ethical principles (Beauchamp et al., 2019) in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4 The six biomedical ethical principles with definitions

Autonomy – AI's role in agency of PwP

It is described by the PwP that AI has the potential to facilitate or hinder autonomy depending on how it is implemented and adopted. AI could increase autonomy through meaningful and personalized insights, both independently and in collaboration with a clinician, and lead to increased knowledge about their condition. PwP hoped that AI could find patterns in symptoms in a better way than themselves and HCPs.

"I recently had a couple of allergic reactions, and I had to get cortisone shots. I noticed straight after ... that my tremor was much better, and I felt better overall. That's interesting. So, I googled histamine cortisone shots ... it turned out that a lot of people searched for antihistamines and cortisone and Parkinson's. So that's just an example of the type of information that I feel is out there" (Female, PwP04, Interview).

To increase the PwP autonomy, the participants considered that all activities need to be actionable. However, if the tools were to be implemented as a strictly clinician-facing tool, it would decrease PwP autonomy.

Beneficence – Maximizing AI's positive impact

Participants identified multiple ways in which AI could offer benefits to their health, particularly by improving data collection, optimizing clinical care, and by enabling early detection and intervention. Since AI could enable automated, continuous data collection and analysis of vast datasets, it is reducing the burden of patients and HCPs. By capturing and analyzing large datasets, AI can unlock valuable real-world data that traditional in-clinic assessments often overlook, transforming previously "trapped" information into actionable knowledge.

"... you have lots of data about symptoms and side effects and ... so on ... something that is very hard for individual people to take in, analysis, but ... that's exactly what machine learning is good at, both detecting patterns in complex sets of data ... but also in using this data

continuously, so that you can predict what is going to happen ... which should be very important information for the healthcare sector..." (Male, PwP03, Interview).

Non-maleficence – “Do no harm”

A major ethical concern of using predictive AI for PD was perceived to be psychological harm, especially regarding risk prediction. There was fear of causing depression or anxiety, and that early risk detection might do more harm than good, given that PD is incurable. However, future advancements leading to improved treatment options and maybe even a cure, then the benefit compensates for the harm of knowing.

“A friend of mine, who I hadn't spoken to in a few years asked me, ‘So what's your prognosis? How are you going to end up in 10 years?’ I had no idea. Nobody can tell me. Maybe that's a good thing” (Female, PwP04, Interview).

Participants emphasized that HCPs must carefully balance potential harms against anticipated benefits when integrating AI into PD care. Since some people would like to know everything, while others are stressed by it. Participants stressed that diagnoses or risk scores should only be delivered by trained professionals, never directly by an app.

Ensuring patient participation in AI development was seen as crucial for aligning technological advancements with patient needs, enhancing usability.

Justice – Fair and equitable use of AI

While participants felt they could potentially benefit from predictive AI and personalized monitoring, they also expressed concerns that not everyone has equal access to the resources necessary to implement AI-generated recommendations. AI and other technical solutions are not suitable for everyone, both regarding disease progression as well as for risk detection. It was also noted that the participants in the patient panel were PwP willing and able to participate and are likely *“the cohort that wants to implement things and make it the best journey”* (Female, PwP11, FG1).

Trust, truthfulness and confidentiality – Transparency and reliability of AI

Privacy and confidentiality were key concerns among participants, who emphasized the need for control over their own data. Participants stressed the need for transparency in data collection, storage, and sharing practices, ensuring that personal health data remains protected and used only with explicit consent.

“I have a genetic mutation. When I got my results, my doctor put it in a sealed envelope and said to save it very carefully, ‘this is the most important information you can have.’ And I actually didn't even think too much about it. But I think for a lot of people, genetic information is important. It's extremely important and private. I think it would be important for [predictive AI] to know what kind of mutation I have, but I would also be afraid that others would know it or would misuse it” (Female, PwP08, FG2).

5.2.2 Patient panel focus groups

As of M8 (February 2024), two focus groups have been carried out with the patient panel (February 15-16, 2024). The aim was to identify and prioritise initial patient-faced user-needs regarding mAI-Health (where the members of the patient panel acted as proxies of PwoP) and mAI-Care tools, which were then reported to the development team (partner SQD). The data was also used for analysis of ethical considerations of using AI in PD management from a PwP perspective (see Section 5.2.1). There were two groups to allow more members to participate while keeping the size small enough for productive conversation and deeper data

collection. The content was similar between the two focus groups, though the facilitators gave the second more time on questions that were not answered thoroughly or at all by the first group to ensure data on all topics of interest. The panel members were divided by which day suited the members better as well as to increase diversity (e.g., a male from France on each day rather than together).

Each focus group consisted of a primary and secondary facilitator as well as one additional project member, who facilitated notetaking. Focus group 1 (1 hour 48 min) consisted of four patient panel members (two females and two males, with an average of 9.5 years since diagnosis, and an average age of 49 years) from three different countries, and focus group 2 (1 hour 43 min) consisted of five patient panel members (three females and two males, with an average of 7.4 years since diagnosis, and an average age of 55 years) from four countries. Overall, one or more PwP participated from England, Germany, Portugal, Sweden with various professional backgrounds, knowledge of AI, and diversity of PD symptoms and treatments. The focus group guide is presented in Appendix I.

An initial combing through the data to identify user-needs from an HCP perspective was done and reported to the developers in WP3 and WP4. The focus groups have been analysed by using thematic analysis (Nowell et al., 2017). The six phases of the analysis were performed, comprising: 1) familiarization of data, 2) categorize the data into meaning units with key words, 3) find patterns within the units to generate themes, 4) themes were named to appropriately fit the aim of the data collection, 5) conceptualization was done through interpretation of keywords, codes and themes, 6) the final result was presented as user needs.

The analysis resulted in two themes and five categories: User interaction, Data collection, PD Risk Assessment Model & PD Progression Predictive Model, Symptom and treatment tracking, and Data visualization. These categories were then tested on HCPs (see 5.2.3).

User interaction

Suggestions for user interaction within mAI-Care and mAI-Health applications is to have a no-type solution based on facial or fingerprint recognition, and that the applications across mobile operating systems should not have differences in functionality. Further, to combat isolation and loneliness, a suggestion from PwP is to offer interactions with other PwP in similar situation through the mAI-Care application.

Data collection

Important aspects for data collection were to have it as automatically as possible, to reduce unnecessary input for the users. Further aspects were an option to choose when during the day data is collected, an element of gamification where the streak count and streak freeze features of the Duolingo language app were referenced, options should be offered to input other relevant data such as menstrual cycle, psychological measures, and daily life activities such as eating with a spoon. For all data collection there should be clear motivation why a specific data entry is relevant, reminders in form of notifications should be provided by the application for data entry, and confirmation of successfully sent data (tests) was also emphasized across the patient board.

PD Risk Assessment Model & PD Progression Predictive Model

The patient panel unanimously felt that risk should not be conveyed by an application (mAI-Health) but rather by a person. For the progression predictive model, the PwP considered that they should be able to review the data input themselves, and there should be as much detailed information as possible about the model and its accuracy.

Symptom and treatment tracking

Data that is relevant for symptom and treatment tracking and has every-day relevance should be visible for the user of the mAI-Care application. The mAI-Health application should take atypical PD into consideration.

Data visualisation

All data should be presented in an accessible and visually appealing manner, also to consider that visualisation of scores need to be contextualized so they are understandable. Important to consider that users can interpret visual elements like graphs in different ways. Clear information should be offered regarding how data security and privacy are safeguarded.

5.2.3 Interviews with healthcare professionals (HCPs)

HCPs, both internal project members and external, recruited with help from clinical partners, were interviewed via Zoom (February-March 2024). The 11 HCPs spanned from five countries (UK, Canada, France, Portugal, and Spain) and various professions (neurologist, sleep specialist, research coordinator, nurse, specialist nurse), and 64% female and 36% male representation. The aim of the interviews was to identify and prioritise HCP identified user-needs. The interview guide began by asking about the HCPs background (diagnosis, treatment, late-stage PD, etc.) and focused on two parts: providing feedback and a rating of initial patient-identified user-needs for the mAI-Health and mAI-care, and self-identifying user-needs for the mAI-Insights platform (see Appendix I). An initial combing through the data to identify user-needs from an HCP perspective was done and reported to the developers in WP3 and WP4. Further a directed content analysis was used for the analysis, since the initial patient-identified user needs were used as key concepts to start the coding process from (Hsieh et al., 2005). Four steps were taken to explore how these key concepts emerged as initial user needs from our stakeholders (HCPs and PwP). The four steps were: 1) to highlight and map the interview data into the key concepts as categories, 2) all highlighted data was coded, 3) data not matching the key concepts/categories were provided with new code, and last 4) an iteratively approach was used to go back and determine whether the new code should be a new category or not.

The analysis resulted in eight categories: Data collection, Daily life, PD Risk Assessment Model, PD Progression Predictive Model, Data visualisation, Symptom and treatment tracking, Reporting, and Alerts.

Data collection

For data collection the HCPs considered it to be good to allow PwP to log sleep problems and quality through a scale within mAI-Care application. Further, other input options should be offered for other relevant data, such as menstrual cycle, exercise, food intake (e.g. proteins), and other individually relevant daily life data (e.g. eating with a spoon). This could be entered manually or selected from a pre-set list. It was considered important with an option to choose when during the day data is collected. To emotionally engage people at risk and PwP, gamification and “fun” features, e.g., counting streaks and using cartoon characters for expressing mood, were viewed positively to enhance compliance. It was noted that those at risk may need more motivation than those already diagnosed. It was also deemed of high importance that confirmation is given once data is submitted, as well as clear motivation why a specific type of data entry is relevant. It could also be relevant for mAI-Care application to provide notifications as reminders for data entry. However, the HCPs thought that as much data as possible should be collected automatically, reducing the input need for the users.

For mAI-Insight, the HCPs considered it being important showing eventual relationship between medication and when symptoms or side effects occurred. To visualise this, bar graphs or something similar to show what time most fluctuations (between tremor and dyskinesias) occurred was preferable.

It is also considered that PwP should be able to choose what (if any) data to share with their ICGs, since there are cultural factors to contemplate here. Even though the HCPs believed it being relevant for the PwP to share data with their carers when having cognitive problems or at a very late stage of PD.

Daily life

To track progression, it was important to consider daily life activities for PwP and people at risk. This could be done by including daily living scores for factors affecting daily life, such as getting dressed, writing, and eating. Here a pre-selected list should be presented to choose 3-4 factors from, to track and then use a score of 0-4 (needing help – no need of help). To present this, a graph should be visualized monthly, to be visualized over time rather than daily. In mAI-Insights this could be presented with a graph with insights from the most difficult daily task a patient is having – how many days per month is it difficult and when during the day is it worsening.

PD Risk Assessment Model

Risk should be presented and explained by a human being rather than through a digital tool. Still, the model could help in explaining and interpreting risk scores for people at risk. For mAI-Health it was considered important to let the user decide by themselves what they wanted to see or not. Overall, the application for risk should be simpler with more automatically collected data and limited active data collection. There should also be limited data visualized in the application, with suggestions of showing tracking streak, days until next appointment, education section, and reduced trends.

PD Progression Predictive Model

In the mAI-Care application the PwP should be able to review the input data themselves, as long as it is presented in an appropriate way. However, there should be limited information on how the model works and its predictions, until it is validated and proven to be accurate. Then detailed information to show the PwP about the model is to prefer.

Data visualisation

If possible, the users could choose the setup for how to visualise their data, e.g. if they prefer to see a summary of their tracked data in a graph or as a bullet point summary (with text). The data should be presented rather as trends over longer period of time to understand the big picture. Important to have visualisation of scores contextualized, to ensure accessibility in data visualisations.

The design of the mAI-Health and mAI-Care applications would preferably include large menus, straightforward actions with minimizing options and information, that could be confusing.

Symptom and treatment tracking

Regarding symptoms and treatment tracking, PwP should be able to opt in or out of tracking certain symptoms. The data being visualized should be personalized based on the main concerns of the PwP, yet avoiding stress or anxiety. When tracking a symptom, the application

should prompt which action to take due to the problem or concern, especially if a deviation is detected. If possible, the mAI-Health application should take atypical PD into consideration.

Reporting

There was consensus that the data should be presented in a pre-visit report summary of maximum one page and contain mostly graphs (quick and easy to visualize) of changes since the last visit. The possibility to extract the report as a PDF or Excel, as well as to click which data to visualize was desired for mAI-Insights. As well as the ability to see how often PwP was logging data and be able to address why patients are not tracking data.

Alerts

There was an agreement that clinicians – a general practitioner (GP) for those undiagnosed and a neurologist for those diagnosed – should be automatically notified of deviations in condition or when the model predicts something above a certain clinical threshold. Most clinicians felt an email would be the most appropriate medium for being notified of such deviations.

Integrating mAI-Insights into the already existing EHR was mentioned as a way to integrate into clinical routine, although another HCP mentioned that in order for this to internationally be implemented, since EHR systems differ between countries and even within countries, a common portal applicable in all countries might be best, even if it means logging into a separate portal. Logging into mAI-Insights prior to a scheduled visit is not seen as a problem for neurologists; however, for GPs, it would be. GPs should instead receive emails of abnormalities and/or the app can suggest and guide the patient to contact their GP in the event of deviations.

5.2.4 Extended user research survey

An online survey on “AI-PROGNOSIS toolkit for Parkinson's disease care” has been open since mid-November 2024. The aim of this survey is to identify the intention to use and compare user-needs and perspectives of AI for PD management across key stakeholders. A survey allows a large number of responses which would broaden and compliment the user needs of different stakeholder groups.

The survey was available in English, French, German, Spanish, and Swedish. Translation was done in accordance with the World Health Organization where a native speaker translated it, and another native speaker back translated the translation for cross-reference, before being reviewed by a third party. Cognitive interviews to test the survey were also conducted. Dissemination was done through the clinician and patient networks of project partners, focusing on European countries where the available languages are spoken, but all countries were welcome to participate. For a comprehensive list of all survey questions, see Appendix IV.

To participate in the survey, respondents had to select one of the following perspectives: (1) person diagnosed with PD, (2) person at risk of developing PD (3) person related to a PwP, (4) ICG to a PwP, or (5) a healthcare professional (HCPs) who works with PD patients. Individuals who either indicated that they are at risk of developing PD or who indicated relation to someone with PD were combined to form the “at risk” sample.

The first 225 responses (as of early May 2025) are summarized below.

Results

The survey responses represent 16 different countries, of which Spain and France compose most (85 and 55 respectively). Nearly half of respondents were people with Parkinson's (PwP) (48%) age 55-74 (49%) and over half of all respondents were female (60%), see **Table 4**. The largest portion were employed part-time (47%) and about a third had a master's degree (29%) and another third a bachelor's (33%) as their highest completed education.

Table 4 Sociodemographic characteristics

Participant perspective (n = 225)	
Person with Parkinson's diagnosis (PwP)	108 (48%)
Persons at risk / related to PwP	28 (12%)
Informal caregiver to PwP	19 (8%)
Healthcare professional working with PwP	70 (31%)
Gender (n = 225)	
Woman	136 (60%)
Man	88 (39%)
Rather not say	2 (1%)
Age (n = 225)	
18 – 24 years	3 (1%)
25 – 34 years	27 (12%)
35 – 44 years	34 (15%)
45 – 54 years	39 (17%)
55 – 64 years	56 (25%)
65 – 74 years	55 (24%)
75 years or older	11 (5%)
Highest level of education (n = 225)	
Primary school	1 (0.4)
Vocational education	25 (11%)
Higher education: Bachelor's	74 (33%)
Higher education: Master's	66 (29%)
Higher education: PhD or similar	40 (18%)
Employment status (n = 225)	
Employed full-time	23 (10%)
Employed part-time	106 (47%)
Retired	72 (32%)
Unemployed	5 (2%)
Disability allowance	9 (4%)
Other	10 (4%)

The majority across all stakeholder groups reported an intermediate level of digital literacy (**Figure 4**), and the lowest reported levels were among ICGs, although they were also the smallest sample.

Figure 4 Self-reported digital literacy by group

Participants expressed strong interest in using AI and digital tools to support PD management. Among those at risk, 23 out of 28 reported being “possibly” or “definitely” interested in using tools such as apps or wearable devices to monitor their risk and manage early symptoms. Similarly, 12 of 19 ICGs indicated interest in using digital tools to support their caregiving responsibilities. Among healthcare professionals, 54 out of 70 reported being “somewhat” or “very” interested in incorporating AI into PD management.

Symptom tracking was a top desired AI feature for all groups, listed for 22/28 people at risk, 88/108 PwP, 51/70 HCPs and 15/19 caregivers. Notably, HCPs valued enhancing patient and caregiver engagement (46/70) above PwP (25/108). Among those at risk, AI-generated lifestyle recommendations to prevent PD were valued above risk reports and health insights (19/24 compared to 14/34). Communication with HCPs ranked second for both persons at risk (17/28) and ICGs (11/19).

The survey reveals strong perceived potential for AI-PROGNOSIS tools and indicates strong overall perceived usefulness and acceptance. For **mAI-Health**, most respondents (59%) felt it would boost their confidence in AI’s ability to monitor and predict PD risk, with even higher levels of agreement (69%) on its usefulness in helping users understand and act on risk reduction advice. Notably, individuals at risk of PD showed strong support, with no one in this group disagreeing. However, attitudes were more divided on whether the tool would foster independence in managing PD risk—while 56% agreed, a significant minority, especially among HCPs, expressed disagreement. Most respondents (59–68%) thought mAI-Health “would be useful” for early detection and managing PD risk factors, and those at risk were especially supportive—with nearly no disagreement. When asked whether they have “a positive attitude towards using” mAI-Health, responses were slightly more modest (around 53–59%), though disagreement was low, suggesting broad receptiveness. HCPs were somewhat more cautious than those at risk (12/70 disagreed), though a clear majority still supported the tool’s value.

In contrast, **mAI-Care**, received even more consistent support. Nearly three-quarters of respondents (72%) felt it would enhance their competence in handling PD progression, and 74% reported an increased intention to use AI tools for this purpose. This sentiment was echoed among both PwP and HCPs, suggesting that AI tools for progression management may meet the practical and psychological needs of both patient and provider groups more effectively than those focused solely on risk. The most enthusiastic responses came in relation to the mAI-Care for managing medication response. A high percentage of participants (77%)

agreed that the tool would improve their ability to understand and follow medication recommendations, and 73% felt it would support their sense of competence in managing medication. These figures were consistently strong across PwP and HCPs alike, pointing to a particularly clear and widely recognized value in using AI to personalize and optimize medication regimens. Over three-quarters of respondents agreed it would be useful for tracking disease progression and managing treatment effects. Importantly, a majority (57%) also believed it would be user-friendly and require minimal effort—key indicators for sustained use. Attitudes toward the app were notably strong, with about two-thirds of respondents planning to use it, including both people with Parkinson's (PwP) and HCPs. These results suggest mAI-Care may be particularly well-positioned to support continuous management of PD symptoms in both clinical and personal settings.

Three-quarters of respondents reported the **mAI-Insights** would be useful for optimizing medication regimens, and 69% reported a positive attitude toward using it. While slightly fewer participants expressed an intention to follow the tool's medication recommendations (63%), disagreement levels were very low. Notably, HCP endorsement was consistently high across all items, underscoring the platform's clinical relevance and perceived effectiveness in helping tailor medication strategies—an area often complex in PD care.

Overall, 66% of PwP respondents expressed intent to use the system “to manage PD,” with a similar proportion (64%) among HCPs. However, when it came to using the system to “monitor and manage the risk of developing PD” enthusiasm was notably lower—only 48% agreed or strongly agreed, and a relatively higher number (39/225) disagreed. This stands out as the least favorable result across all areas assessed. In contrast, responses were more optimistic about tracking disease progression and managing medications. Around 69% intended to use the system for monitoring PD progression, and 66% planned to use it for medication management, reflecting stronger buy-in for tools that support ongoing care and treatment. These findings suggest that while preventive applications of AI may face more hesitation, there is a clear appetite for tools that assist with active disease management and clinical decision-making.

5.2.5 Targeted (short) user research survey

The aim of this complimentary survey, titled, “Opinions and experiences of Persons with Parkinson's on artificial intelligence (AI) and self-tracking” is to test user-needs identified through qualitative research, on a large scale through a quick and more detailed online survey. The survey is composed of Likert items, multiple choice, and free-text questions. For a comprehensive list of the questions, see Appendix IV. The survey was published in April 2025 and the results ($n = 94$) from June 2025 are described below.

The survey is currently available in English, Spanish, French and Swedish, and was created in English, then translated using the EU Survey platform's built-in AI translation and then checked and correct by a native speaker. The quantitative data was analyzed descriptively, and the qualitative free text was analyzed using contend analysis.

Results

Respondents were people with Parkinson's (PwP) aged 43-85 (mean 64, median 65) and majority male (42 women, 52 men). There was diversity in terms of years living with PD, with a span of 0-27 years since being diagnosed with PD, (mean 7, median 6). The majority had completed higher education (72.34%), with 39.36% having completed a master's degree.

Prognosis

74% agreed/strongly agree that they would be interested to know their "PD prognosis in terms of future overall motor condition" though slightly fewer 68% wanted to know their prognosis "in terms of development of future disease milestones" (e.g., cognitive dysfunction, hallucinations, freezing of gait, or dysphagia). In terms of insights, 93% were interested in knowing which factors may affect their PD prognosis, but half 50% (47/94) would only want to know if they could do something about it, i.e., actionable insights. Many PwP commented that "the focus should be on what can be influenced by both me and the healthcare system. This can be done both individually and through information efforts in various forums."

Symptom and medication tracking

The majority (77%) felt graphs would help understand their symptoms better though under half (44%) agreed/strongly agreed that gamification (e.g., streak count, rewards) of self-tracking would help motivate them to consistently use the system for monitoring PD. In terms of time commitment, nearly half (49%) would be willing to spend 30 minutes a week on digital tests that measure cognitive and motor symptoms, and most of the others were willing to spend less. 74% wanted to be able to self-select 2-3 daily tasks to track (e.g. eating soup with a spoon) and nearly as many (70%) would like the option to manually enter medications and receive reminders.

The most desired reasons for predictive AI were to receive personalized treatment recommendations (81/94), followed by predicting disease progression (63/94) and tracking symptoms (61/94). The top symptoms desired to track were balance, posture and gait (via interactive camera-based tests on a smartphone) (40/94), slowness of finger and hand movement (via a smartwatch and smartphone) (39/94), followed by dyskinesias (via a smartwatch) (39/94). The majority (74%) felt that educational content about how AI prediction works and uses data would increase trust in the system.

5.3 Co-creation findings

To further refine the user needs, involving stakeholders, and collect feedback for designing the AI-PROGNOSIS tools, co-creation activities have been performed.

5.3.1 AI Design & Specification workshops with persons with Parkinson's (PwP)

As part of the projects' co-creation initiative, two workshops were held between technical partners (AUTH, AING), bioethics partners (UOXF), UU, and the patient panel on the topic of trustworthy AI. The workshops were held on two separate occasions in M9 (March 2024) with a different diverse sub-group of patient panel members (6 PwP in workshop one, 5 PwP in workshop two) in each workshop. The PwP consisted of four females and seven males, with an average time since diagnosis of 8.4 ± 5.54 years. The first focused on the mAI-Health tool and the second on mAI-Care.

The structure of the workshop began with a round of introductions from everyone and then an introduction from AUTH into the meaning of trustworthy AI. An overview of the tools of focus (mAI-Health or -Care) was given and an introduction to personas (see Appendix III) that could be referenced when answering the questions. The workshop was then split into two smaller groups using Zoom "break out rooms" in which there was a moderator from UU, 1-2 developers from AUTH, 2-3 PwP (mixed gender and nationalities), and in some groups, an ethicist from UOXF. The smaller groups allowed both technical partners and PwP to discuss issues of trustworthiness in AI and co-create solutions for the project. The discussion was organized around five topic areas: trustworthy AI design, human autonomy in healthcare and self-care, fairness and equality, explainability & transparency, and other considerations.

The collected data was part of the user research and was analyzed with an inductive thematic analysis process (Braun et al, 2006). After familiarizing oneself with the data, an initial set of codes was developed (see **Figure 5**). These codes were then organized into five major themes and sub-themes: AI Trust and Security (Theme 1), AI Transparency and Education (Theme 2), AI Bias (Theme 3), Human Oversight (Theme 4), and AI Psychological Impact (Theme 5).

Figure 5 The 2-outer circle describes the results from the thematic analysis, including themes (inner part of the circle), subthemes (middle part of the circle), and corresponding codes (outer part of the circle) (Alves et al, 2025).

AI Trust and Security (Theme 1)

Integrating AI for PD diagnosis and management raised some concerns about robust security measures and system reliability, with insecure platforms and misuse of data. It was considered important to build trust among the users, as well as important with the importance of consistency in AI outputs. As highlighted by one participant:

“If the process isn’t very accurate and if said somebody had Parkinson’s when they didn’t, a false positive, that can be pretty untrustworthy” (PwP #1, workshop #1).

AI Transparency and Education (Theme 2)

To make the process of AI system clear, transparency was essential for all relevant stakeholders, as an aim to prevent misconceptions. Educational resources were also

important as aid to the users, to foster informed engagement. In this line, one participant noted the following:

“There must be a support educational program to inform what AI actually is because the generic opinion about it at the moment is negative” (PwP #3, workshop #1).

AI Bias (Theme 3)

It is necessary to have robust bias mitigation strategies according to the PwP. Still, AI could enhance fairness in medical diagnoses by eliminating human elements such as prejudice that might affect decision-making. One patient noted:

“AI will bring more fairness to the diagnosis because it’s an algorithm, so it works equally for everybody. There is no prejudice.” (PwP #2, workshop #1)

Human Oversight (Theme 4)

There is considered to be a need for AI to complement human decisions, rather than to replace HCPs, since PwP did not want to have an impersonal relationship with healthcare. This will ensure better support for HCP-patient relationships and preserve trust. Human oversight adds a layer of reassurance and accountability, as acknowledged by one participant:

“Yeah, I tend to think that if AI is getting more and more accurate results, I would give more trust to the AI decisions over time. We tend to give more trust in a human healthcare professional.” (PwP #4, workshop #2)

The PwP considered that they would trust HCP’s treatment and diagnosis decisions being informed by AI, but only if the reasoning was explained. Something expected regardless of whether AI was used or not.

AI Psychological Impact (Theme 5)

The PwP stresses there could be psychological impact of AI integration in PD care with potential distress caused by AI-generated diagnoses, as well as emotional burden of AI predictions without actionable outcomes. Further, PwPs’ attitudes towards AI are influenced by psychological fear, with uncertainty about the AI advancement, as expressed by one participant:

“I think there’s a lot of fear about AI. And I think it’s worth considering where AI is already used, for example for auto segmentation or an MRI scan.” (PwP #2, workshop #1).

As a summary, the integration of AI in PD management raises concerns about security, reliability, and data misuse, making trust-building essential. Consistency and transparency in AI outputs are crucial to prevent misconceptions, alongside educational resources to help users engage meaningfully. While AI has the potential to enhance fairness by reducing human bias in medical decisions, it should complement – not replace – HCPs. AI-assisted decisions must be explained clearly to maintain trust. To mitigate the above concerns, AI should be integrated thoughtfully and support informed healthcare decisions. Further details of the analysis can be found in the forthcoming article of Alves et al. (2025).

5.3.2 AI Design & Specification workshops with HCPs

One workshop was held with four external HCPs, UU as facilitators, technical partners (AUTH, KUL), the research team FMH, and one bioethics partner (UOXF) in November 2024 (06/11/2024), by using Zoom. As well as a second workshop with two external HCPs, UU, technical partners (AUTH, KUL), the research team FMH, and one bioethics partner (UOXF) in November 2024 (11/11/2024), by using Zoom. The mean age of the HCPs was 43.33±14.61

years and an average of 15.00±14.63 years of experience working within PD. See the questions in appendix I.

The data was used for user research with the same analysis that was performed as for the AI Design & Specification workshops with PwP (see Figure 3).

AI Trust and Security (Theme 1)

The participants acknowledge data collection, storage, and restricted access to prevent privacy concerns and data misuse. Inadequate data protection could otherwise affect insurance coverage, as highlighted by one HCP:

“There is always a risk in the use of this data, how to collect it, how to store it, and who can access it. This needs to be very clear with strictly restricted access to prevent privacy concerns. ... This data is very strong and could be used by companies to deny patients insurance.” (HCP #1, workshop #1)

There should be a balanced approach for AI integration into PD management, according to the HCPs. It has benefits, but the limitations need to be recognized as well. HCPs should be educated about AI systems to better understand how AI works and what data is based on.

AI Transparency and Education (Theme 2)

With continuous education on AI that would empower HCPs, they are more likely to view AI as a support for e.g. decision-making, rather than a replacement, as noted by one HCP:

“Doctors normally are very against things we don’t see. ... If we understand how AI works, we can demystify it. AI shouldn’t be seen as something unreachable and incomprehensible.” (HCP #2, workshop #1)

AI Bias (Theme 3)

One bias mentioned was that racial and gender bias in healthcare algorithms was a challenge, and incomplete datasets and variability in clinical assessments. Incomplete datasets posed a challenge for a more comprehensive assessment, especially if HCPs trust in the data and do not ask about all symptoms from the patient. The assessment variability could further include bias in AI models. Models that must be trained in consistent and reliable data to provide accurate predictions. Furthermore, ethical use of AI in healthcare must be provided, since there could be cases when AI gathers data and uncovers sensitive information, that patients would not disclose to HCPs. In this line, one HCP mentioned the following:

“AI could gather data from many sources and make connections that the patient never disclosed to the doctor. This could be very dangerous.” (HCP #4, workshop #2)

Human Oversight (Theme 4)

The participants emphasized the relevance of human judgment and accountability in assisted AI decision-making, and that final interpretation is the HCPs’ responsibility, as noted:

“The doctor has the final responsibility, and AI is just a tool – like an MRI or CT scan. You would never blame the CT machine, but you would always hold the doctor responsible for interpreting it.” (HCP #3, workshop #1)

With clear implementation guidelines in clinical settings, the HCPs would better understand the role of AI and do not feel imposed to use it. This could also lead to mitigating the risk associated with over-reliance on AI, while still benefiting from its output.

AI Psychological Impact (Theme 5)

The HCPs stressed the need for thoughtful communication of AI results and the relevance of sharing information that might not lead to actionable outcomes. It is considered their role to not lose the human aspect of care in the integration of technology, and to guide patients. In this context, one HCP stated the following:

“We want to predict if someone will develop PD, but if we can’t change the outcome, what is the goal of giving this news now? It’s a hard thing to take in.” (HCP #2, workshop #3)

Still, the participants considered it important to involve the patients in shared decision-making with increased trust.

As a summary, HCPs acknowledge the importance of data security to prevent privacy concerns and potential insurance implications. Concerns were raised about bias in healthcare algorithms, highlighting the need for comprehensive datasets. They advocate for a balanced approach in integrating AI into PD management, recognizing both its advantages and limitations. Continuous AI education is essential, allowing HCPs to view AI as a support tool. Clear implementation guidelines can prevent imposed AI use and reduce over-dependence while retaining AI’s benefits. Further details of this analysis can be found in the forthcoming article (Alves, B., et al, 2025).

5.3.3 UI/UX design workshops with PwP

The UI/UX design workshops were intended to further investigate the user needs and experiences, and to understand the intended users’ preferences regarding user interface (UI). A simplified directed content analysis (Hsieh et al., 2005) was performed after each workshop, to further refine identified user needs and identify if there were unmet needs. The identified and up-dated user needs were used as key concepts to start the coding process from.

Two workshops were held with the patient panel (n=4 and n=4), UU, and technical partner SQD in October 2024 (22/10/2024 & 23/10/2024), by using Zoom. For the first session the participants represented four different countries (Sweden, France, UK, and Portugal), had a mean age of 57, and with mean years since diagnosis of 5. For the second session the participants represented three different countries (Germany, UK, and Spain), had a mean age of 51, and with mean years since diagnosis of 10.

See Appendix I to view the questions and mockups for the workshops, and the collected data from both sessions was analyzed by using a simplified directed content analysis, in regard to the mockups and refinements of user needs.

- For the PD progression model, it was rather unclear how it could interact with the patients and the usefulness of it. To decide how useful it could be, the participants needed to know what data it was based on. Still, it was deemed to be more important for e.g. neurologists, even though visualization of data over time was something useful.
- To visualize the slowness of movement was something valuable for some of the participants. Especially if it showed an average over time and on an individual basis. The automatic function of the smartwatch capturing this stage of PD, was also understood as valuable data for them to have and to communicate to HCPs. It was considered good with objective data rather than subjective as often occurs, even though some thoughts came up regarding accuracy of the smartwatch and how it could measure slowness and dyskinesia. It was also mentioned that warnings of freezing of gate would be a good feature to have.

- Regarding human activity recognition, the participants considered it to be relevant and motivating to have this function. However, the phrasing of “human activity” was considered to be rephrased. Overall, since the PwP needs to know what is good for them or not, the activity needs to be specified.
- For rest tremor detection and amplitude assessment, some participants would like to track this for themselves, to be connected to their lifestyle. Others considered it to be important to have this connected to HCPs. It was also a question about whether this was connected to heart rate or not, since tremor could be worse when getting excited. For UI, the participants considered bar-charts rather than line-charts in the interface.
- The PwP mentioned that for dyskinesia detection assessment, there are different types of dyskinesia (on/off), hence it is important to specify that. Also, to measure dyskinesia in an active situation. It would be interesting to see trends with a comparison with other activities, to better understand if they are improving or getting worse. For UI it was mentioned that it would be preferable to see different symptoms for one scale (in this case hour bar-charts).
- To have a balance/posture assessment makes sense for some of the PwP, since it was reported that one side effect was bad posture that resulted in a lack of balance, which was very troublesome. Others did not understand how posture could be measured, and what does it really mean – what is a good posture, and it would not be relevant if it did not have that as a side effect. It was also mentioned that it can be challenging to set up the phone to record this, and in the end get meaningful data.
- Regardless of passive or active cognitive assessments, the participants did not think it should be shown, since it might be data that is not motivating them or giving them hope. Especially if they are not receiving any feedback. This kind of data is very sensitive and could lead to not wanting results, e.g. being considered not to function in different situations.
- When showing mockups for smartwatch data sync, it was considered important to know right away if something is not working and the smartwatch is not properly synced. It was considered good with an alert if that occurred, as well as a solution to act upon the notification. For this it was also important to show the time and date in the application, for the last data sent. Regarding data from mAI-Care that is connected to mAI-Insights, it was considered that it should be initiated by PwP to be in control over the data. Of course, it would be preferable if it could be automated and not necessarily initiated by a human. Further some preferred the use of QR-code as input, if not shaking too much using it.
- To refine the user needs and requirements, there was a discussion regarding sharing data from mAI-Care to ICGs and HCPs. Here it was considered important to opt out and to select which data to share with others. Overall, it was deemed positive to share everything with ICGs.

As a conclusion, the participants would only like to view graphs that help them to act on a symptom, rather than only for information. If showing graphs that present a score, do have details about how a score is calculated. Further UI aspects were that not all graphs need to look the same, since that can be confusing. Also, the graphs should be tailored to match the data being shown. Still, it depends on what stage you are at in your disease, whether graphs are useful or not. The PwP would prefer for the system not to show cognitive data.

Two further workshops with focus on mAI-Care and mAI-Health were held with the patient panel (n=5 and n=2) and UU, SQD, and technical partners (AUTH, KUL) in April 2025

(28/04/2025 & 29/04/2025), by using Zoom. For the first workshop the patient panel participants represented three different countries (UK, France, and Sweden) and had a mean age of 59. The mean years since diagnosis was 9. For the second workshop two countries were represented (Spain and France) and the participants had a mean year of 52 and mean years since diagnosis was 13.

See Appendix I to view the questions and mockups for the workshops, and the collected data from both sessions was analyzed by using a simplified directed content analysis, in regard to the mockups and refinements of user needs.

- Overall, the participants described that their uncertainty level is quite high and they have often peculiar symptoms. Since this is very subjective, this is a big challenge for people living with PD.
- When it comes to user engagement regarding mAI-Health, that will require minimum engagement and a passive form of interaction. The participants thought they would like to be logged in, as well as wearing the smartwatch and answering the questionnaire. This is to receive notifications from HCPs and to see that data is collected correctly. It would also be motivating to receive feedback in the form of statistics for the wear time of the smartwatch. Still, before being diagnosed, the PwP considered that people at risk do not tend to be so interested in the diagnosis, so it could be difficult to find the users.
- The motivation aspects for mAI-Care are the same as for mAI-Health, but to be careful with what words are being used. E.g. gamification is not a good word for describing engagement and motivation, since having PD is not a game.
- For self-reporting within the application, it would be good to have reminders to input self-reported data or daily life activities, as it was considered good to have a pull-down menu to choose from. The self-reporting data was understood as something they could learn from, especially if the system detected when something new happened. This could help them understand the “new” symptoms, as well as targeting treatment towards it. To monitor progression takes time, and therefore it is necessary to be patient to gain a pattern out of it. A motivator to continue monitoring and using the application could be to have an HCP or an ICG “controlling” the user, so the tasks are being performed.
- There were no comments regarding whether patients must allow which data to share with their HCPs, within the system. mAI-Care must, however, provide a clear motivation to the user why a specific data entry is needed.
- Also showing actionable data is preferable by PwP, e.g. data from physical activity could be more important for PwP, and data from tremor and dyskinesia is more important for HCPs. Still, if less rest tremor or higher level of intensity is visualized, it would be helpful for PwP since having tremor often is connected to confusing symptoms and is not always easy for PwP to detect. It was also considered important with early detection of dyskinesia to get the correct medication and dosage. Overall, it was considered important to show data for physical activity, rest tremor of hand, and dyskinesia.

5.3.4 UI/UX design workshops with HCPs

One workshop was held with focus on mAI-Insights with two external HCPs, UU, SQD, technical partners (AUTH, KUL, AING, CERTH), and project healthcare partner (CHUT/France) in January 2025 (28/01/2025), by using Zoom. The two external HCPs

represented one country (Germany), worked as general practitioner and movement disorder specialist. Mean years of age was 50 and mean years of working as HCPs was 19.

A second workshop was held with focus on mAI-Insights with project healthcare partners (FIN, TUD, CHUT), UU, SQD, and technical partners (AUTH, KUL, AING, CERTH) in February 2025 (24/02/2025), by using Zoom.

See Appendix I to view the questions and mockups for the workshops, and the collected data from both sessions was analyzed by using a simplified directed content analysis, in regard to refinements of the user needs and requirements.

- The screening and prediction system will generate reports accessible through mAI-Insights. These reports will include digital risk score, explanations of the model's decision-making process, confidence levels, and PD risk-related digital biomarkers. Discussing the risk report within mAI-Insights leads to different needs from the HCPs regarding when the risk report should be sent to them. Therefore, the report should be customized to produce a risk score for the patient and then be sent within a timeframe suitable for each country and profession. This timeframe could be a span from three months (preferable for GPs in Germany) up to 12 months. It was discussed by the project partners (all representing secondary healthcare) that nothing meaningful would have happened regarding PD risk within less than one year. It was also mentioned that a longer period would decrease the risk of false positives. Further, it was mentioned that the score needs to be clear, so it is understandable what number represents a high or low risk. The participant also valued to receive the probability of a person developing PD within one, two, or even five years. The HCPs also considered it interesting to see whether RBD as a biomarker was detected, as well as to add hyposmia and hypotension.
- For the PD progression report, it would be good to visualize a pie chart of key predictors for a specific patient based on the last six months. Further UI aspects were to show the probability of a person progressing fast or slow with a score indicated in a bar chart, and there was also necessary with a definition of fast/slow progression, since there is no clinical definition for this. It was also deemed important that progression is not only about motor symptoms, but also to define progression for non-motor symptoms such as cognition. One suggestion to measure the progression in non-motor symptoms was to investigate the time to event and the disability milestones. Further UI recommendation was to only show percentage and not confidence interval, since it would only confuse the users.
- When discussing the PD medication response report, it was mentioned that the only side effects relevant here were those related to medication response, such as the presence of dyskinesia, hallucination, impulse control disorder, and dopamine dysregulation. A good feature in the medication response model would be to see the probability for progression when keeping current medication, or what happens if the medication is changed. The goal for this would be to reduce the on/off time for the patient, and reduce the dyskinesia time, even though it is difficult to state if someone has dyskinesia or not.
- For all reports, there will be a printable PDF file to share with PwP. The HCPs did not consider it necessary for them to have it as a PDF. Alerts within the system were also discussed, that falls and hospitalizations (e.g., due to pneumonia) would produce a red flag/alarm in the system. However, for this version of the application the HCPs agreed

that there will be no alerts, other than those for lack of adherence – e.g., not wearing the smartwatch.

- Regarding self-reported data, the most discussed aspect was sleeping quality. Here it would be interesting to ask about insomnia, restless legs, nocturia, waking up several times, waking up early, pain at night, rigidity, and sleepwalking. This could be reported weekly or every month, and there should be a list of sleep symptoms (problems) to choose from. This will be part of daily life activities. There were some concerns about requiring too much information from the patients, and one solution for that was to make this section optional. If the patients choose the top three activities from the UPDR part II and score the activities from 0-4 based on how much help was needed, they will be doing it from their objectives and not being demanded to do it.

Third workshop: To let the project healthcare partners express their thoughts on the development of mAI-Care, another workshop was held with FIN, TUD, and CHUT together with UU, SQD, and technical partners (AUTH, KUL, AING, CERTH) in April 2025 (01/04/2025), by using Zoom.

See Appendix I to view the questions and mockups for the workshops, being the same as for the PwP-workshops in October 2024. The collected data from the session was analyzed by using a simplified directed content analysis, in regard to the mockups and refinements of user needs.

- Overall, the HCPs considered it important to let the PwP as users of mAI-Care choose which data to share with their HCP, as well as the application to have a clear motivation for why a specific type of data entry is needed.
- Further, the participants did not see the use for PwP to see the PD progression prediction, which goes in line with the PwPs' opinions.
- However, regarding slowness of movement, the patients considered it to be helpful, while the HCPs did not see it being useful for the PwP, if it was not actionable data. It is always dangerous to show patients data regarding things they cannot change, since it could create anxiety.
- The HCPs agreed with the PwP that human activity recognition is useful and good to show, as well as dyskinesia detection. This is data that will not lead to anxiety.
- The opposite was considered regarding cognitive assessment (active and passive), both HCPs and PwP agreed that cognitive data should not be shown.

5.3.5 Hands-on experience and feedback workshops with PwP

Hands-on workshops have been performed as a final round of co-creation workshops, to provide final feedback to the development of the applications. The objective of the workshops is for the participants as potential users to acquire a brief overview of the actual applications and to provide feedback. The feedback consisted of usefulness and if it was understandable.

For mAI-Health, a first hands-on workshop with two PwP from the patient panel as proxy for people at risk was held together with SQD in April 2025 (29/04/2025), by using Zoom. Two countries were represented (Spain and France) and the participants had a mean year of 52 and mean years since diagnosis was 13.

- There were some clarifications for the PwP regarding how to sign in or if to register to get hold of the application, that there will be a code from HCPs recommending you as

a person at risk to use the application. The participants recommended the use of QR codes, or even both.

- The PwP also reacted to the text “I wake up around...”, since they wake up several times in one night. Still, since it only was for the smartwatch to start its notification time, they considered that the text could remain.
- There was also some consideration about data collection and storage, such as addresses or other personal data. It was also important to know within the application why they should be using it as a motivational factor.

Other than this, the participants were content with mAI-Health and the design of it.

For mAI-Care, two hands-on workshops (10/06/2025 and 13/06/2025) have been performed with the patient panel. The feedback focused on the setup process and monthly tests.

- Participants appreciated that passively collected data could be viewed at different intervals.
- Participants also recommended changing the wording of input of one’s sleep hours upon app set up to “do-not-disturb hours during which you may be asleep” since PwP so commonly experiences sleep disturbances and varied hours.

6 Updated identified user needs

From the collected data, described above (Section 5), user needs for each AI-PROGNOSIS tool (Section 2.4) are defined.

6.1 mAI-Health mobile app

For mAI-Health app, updated user needs are described in **Table 5**. Those in red have been dropped, with a brief justification under “Priority”, after feedback received from the extended user research and co-creation activities that took following D2.1 ‘Initial report on user research and co-creation’.

Table 5 Updated user needs for PwoP and HCPs – mAI-Health mobile app. User needs highlighted with red color have been dropped. N/A: not applicable.

Need ID	Need description	Source	Priority
UR.mH.01 - User interaction			
UR.mH.01.01	For authentication, a no-type solution based on facial or fingerprint recognition should be used, such as Passkey.	Patient panel	N/A (log-in to app scarcely required as user stays logged in)
UR.mH.01.02	The iOS and Android apps should not have differences in functionality.	Patient panel	N/A - iOS will not be implemented
UR.mH.02 – Data collection			
UR.mH.02.01	As much data as possible should be collected automatically, reducing the input required of users.	Patient panel	High

UR.mH.02.02	Data that has everyday relevance should be shown to users in-app.	Patient panel	N/A - no data will be shown for mAI-Health
UR.mH.02.03	Data shown in-app should be presented in an accessible and visually appealing manner.	Patient panel	N/A - no data will be shown for mAI-Health
UR.mH.02.04	There should be an option to choose when during the day data is collected.	Patient panel	High
UR.mH.02.05	Elements of gamification could be added to the app.	Patient panel	N/A - gamified elements were not needed
UR.mH.02.06	Elements of gamification should be customizable to correspond with users' preferences.	Patient panel	
UR.mH.02.07	With gamification, a 'streak freeze' option should be available, allowing users to skip a day without losing their streak.	Patient panel	
UR.mH.02.08	Input options should be offered for other relevant data, such as menstrual cycle, psychological measures, and individually relevant task data, such as 'eating soup with a spoon'.	Patient panel	N/A - not applicable for PwoP
UR.mH.02.09	Clear motivations should be provided regarding why a specific type of data entry is relevant.	Patient panel	High
UR.mH.02.10	Optional notifications/reminders should be given by the app for data entry.	Patient panel	High
UR.mH.02.11	Confirmation should be given by the app that data has been successfully uploaded.	Patient panel	High
UR.mH.03 - PD risk assessment model			
UR.mH.03.01	Risk scores should be presented and explained by a human being who has been trained for that situation.	Patient panel	High
UR.mH.04 – Explainable insights			
UR.mH.04.01	The app should also take atypical PD into consideration.	Patient panel	N/A - deemed not possible by clinical partners
UR.mH.05 – User interface			
UR.mH.05.01	The user interface should be very basic and easy to navigate and understand.	Patient panel	High
UR.mH.05.02	Users' data entry should be simplified as possible.	Patient panel	High
UR.mH.05.03	Safeguards should be implemented, making it impossible for users to enter data correctly.	Patient panel	High
UR.mH.05.04	Special care should be given to ensuring accessibility to the user interface.	Patient panel	High
UR.mH.06 – Data Visualization			
UR.mH.06.01	Patients can choose in settings/app setup to see summary of their tracked data in graph or text/bullet point summary format.	Patient panel	N/A - No data will be displayed

UR.mH.06.02	Patient data should not be presented to patients as plain numbers but rather visual and/or descriptive (text).	Patient panel	
UR.mH.06.03	Patient data should be presented as big picture trend i.e. symptoms over past month, not over 1 day, definitely not hour by hour.	Patient panel	
UR.mH.07 – Symptom and Treatment Tracking			
UR.mH.07.01	Confirm detected concerning symptoms e.g. your watch detected that you have fallen recently, is this correct? Y/N	Patient panel, HCPs	The data collection from the smartwatch will not tell the user to act on something, but HCPs will contact if something abnormal is detected
UR.mH.07.02	Prompt with action to take e.g. to schedule a visit e.g. "your watch reminds you to schedule a visit if you are falling more often".	HCPs	
UR.mH.07.03	When deviation is detected, ask about common symptoms for infection etc. which are common non-PD culprits for worsening PD symptoms e.g. contact primary care if experiencing any of following: fever, pain upon urination (UTI), etc.	Patient panel	
UR.mH.05 - Education			
UR.mH.08.01	Education module/database to look up recommendations to self-manage common symptoms e.g. constipation, poor sleep, etc. and when to seek HCP.	Patient panel, Survey.	High

6.2 mAI-Care mobile app

For mAI-Care Mobile Application, updated user needs from PwP and HCPs are described in **Table 6**. Several user needs are the same as for mAI-Health Mobile Application. Those in red have been dropped, with a brief justification under “Priority”, and those in green are new user needs identified.

Table 6 Updated user needs for PwP and HCPs – mAI-care mobile app. User needs highlighted with green color are newly identified and those with red color have been dropped. N/A: not applicable.

Need ID	Need description	Source	Priority
UR.mC.01 – User interaction			
UR.mC.01.01	For authentication, a no-type solution based on facial or fingerprint recognition should be used, such as Passkey.	Patient panel	N/A - Requirement does not apply
UR.mC.01.02	The iOS and Android apps should not have differences in functionality.	Patient panel	N/A - iOS will not be implemented
UR.mC.01.03	To combat isolation and loneliness, the app should offer interactions with other PwPs in a similar situation.	Patient panel	High
UR.mC.02 - Data collection			
UR.mC.02.01	As much data as possible should be collected automatically, minimizing the input required of users.	Patient panel	High
UR.mC.02.02	There should be an option to choose when during the day data is collected.	Patient panel,	High

		HCPs	
UR.mC.02.03	Elements of gamification could be added to the app.	Patient panel	Low
UR.mC.02.04	Elements of gamification should be reward-based.	Patient panel	Low
UR.mC.02.05	With gamification, a 'streak freeze' option should be available, allowing users to skip a day without losing their streak	Patient panel	This kind of elements were not needed
UR.mC.02.06	Clear motivations should be provided regarding why a specific type of data entry is relevant.	Patient panel, Survey	High
UR.mC.02.07	Notifications/reminders should be given by the app for data entry.	Patient panel	Medium/High
UR.mC.02.08	Confirmation should be given by the app that data has been successfully uploaded.	Patient panel, HCPs	High
UR.mC.02.09	The app should collect data and give positive reinforcement for actions targeted at slowing down symptom progression.	Patient panel, Survey	High
UR.mC.02.10	Allow PwP to log sleep problems (insomnia, restless legs, nocturia, waking up several times, waking up early, pain at night, rigidity, sleepwalking).	Patient panel, Survey	High
UR.mC.03 - PD progression predictive model			
UR.mC.03.01	PwP should be able to review the input data themselves.	Patient panel	N/A - unclear to have as a user need
UR.mC.03.02	There should be as much detailed information as possible about the model and how accurate it is.	Patient panel	Medium
UR.mC.04 - Symptom and treatment tracking			
UR.mC.04.01	Data that has everyday relevance should be shown to users in-app.	Patient panel, Survey	High
UR.mC.04.02	Data shown in-app should be presented in an accessible and visually appealing manner.	Patient panel, Survey	High
UR.mC.04.03	Input options should be offered for other relevant data, such as menstrual cycle, psychological measures, and daily life activities such as 'eating soup with a spoon'.	Patient panel, Survey	High
UR.mC.05 - User interface			
UR.mC.05.01	Data visualization should take into consideration that users can interpret visual elements like graphs very differently.	Patient panel	High
UR.mC.05.02	Special care should be given to ensuring accessibility in data visualizations.	Patient panel	High
UR.mC.05.03	Visualization of data needs to be relevant, understandable, and contextualized.	Patient panel	High
UR.mC.06 – Clinical data integration			

UR.mC.06.01	There should be as much information as possible about the clinical data used, what it contributes, and so forth.	Patient panel	High
UR.mC.07 – User and caregiver access			
UR.mC.07.01	PwP users should be able to choose what (if any) information to share with ICGs.	Patient panel, Survey	N/A - for current system
UR.mC.07.02	Clear information should be offered regarding how data security and privacy are safeguarded.	Patient panel	High
UR.mC.07.03	A medication management feature should be included (input data, reminders, etc.)	Patient panel, Survey	High
UR.mC.08 – Education			
UR.mC.08.01	Education module for common symptoms e.g. constipation, poor sleep, etc. Add note that if not better seek HCP.	Patient panel, Survey	High

6.3 mAI-Insights HCP clinical platform

For mAI-Insights HCP clinical platform, updated user needs from HCPs are described in **Table 7**.

Table 7 Updated user needs for HCPs – mAI-Insights HCP clinical platform.

Need ID	Need description	Source	Priority
UR.ml.01 - Reporting			
UR.ml.01.01	Enable on-demand report generation to ensure clinician has a patient summary report at all visits.	HCPs	Medium
UR.ml.01.02	Generating a report should be fast, preferably in the encounter.	HCPs	High
UR.ml.01.03	The format of the report should be in PDF or Excel.	HCPs	Medium/High
UR.ml.01.04	The report should be visualized in a pre-existing portal or otherwise by email.	HCPs	High
UR.ml.01.05	Graphs/trends should be used for visualization.	HCPs	High
UR.ml.01.06	The visualization of the report should follow the structure of a traffic light, i.e., 'red' denotes concerning, 'yellow' denotes monitor, 'green' denotes good.	HCPs	High
UR.ml.01.07	There should be comparisons e.g., now vs last visit, or now vs 6 months ago (e.g., value x is -20% compared to the previous check).	HCPs	High
UR.ml.01.08	The brevity should be a month-to-month or week-to-week option (not a day-to-day trend).	HCPs	High
UR.ml.01.09	It should be easy to filter out information to include in the report.	HCPs	High

UR.ml.01.10	It should be possible to see how often the patient is logging data (how much data the model and report is based on and address why the patient is not tracking).	HCPs	High
UR.ml.02 - Data collection			
UR.ml.02.01	A graph showing the relationship between medication and when symptoms/side effects occurred should be included.	HCPs	High
UR.ml.02.02	Include a bar graph, or something similar, to show what time there are most fluctuations-dyskinesias, meaning most fluctuations between tremor and dyskinesias.	HCPs	High
UR.ml.02.03	Include data to show the bradykinesia score.	HCPs	High
UR.ml.02.04	Include data to show the dyskinesia score.	HCPs	High
UR.ml.02.05	Include sleep data for PwP, to find sleep problems that develop (insomnia, restless legs, nocturia, waking up several times, waking up early, pain at night, rigidity, sleepwalking).	HCPs	Medium
UR.ml.03 - Daily life overview			
UR.ml.03.01	Include lifestyle score as an option to receive averaged or separate 3-4 lifestyle factors (composite or individual score).	HCPs	Medium/High
UR.ml.03.02	To present insights from the "most difficult daily task" as a proportion and graph, e.g., 3 of 30 days patient had (most) difficulty with 'x' in the morning and a graph of most difficult tasks over months.	HCPs	High
UR.ml.03.03	To include a daily living score, e.g., dressing, eating, personal hygiene (+1/-1) improved/worsened.	HCPs	High
UR.ml.04 - Alerts/Functions			
UR.ml.04.01	Alert function that notifies clinician upon detection of extreme health changes in patient.	HCPs	High

6.4 AI-assisted Medication Decision support (AIMED) Module

For the AIMED module, updated user needs from HCPs are described in **Table 8**.

Table 8 Updated user needs for HCPs – AIMED module for medication decision support

Need ID	Need description	Source	Priority
UR.mM.01 - Data collection			
UR.mM.01.01	PwP can self-input medication info (what they are prescribed, when take it, etc.) vs. only input by HCP via their portal (PwP)	Patient panel, Survey	High
UR.mM.01.02	PwP can self-report common/key lifestyle factors (e.g., stress, diet) which can impact medication response	HCPs, Patient panel, Survey	High
UR.mM.02 - User interface			

UR.mM.02.01	Allow medication regimen (type/dose/timing) to be compared to observed signs/symptoms	HCPs, Patient panel, Survey	High
UR.mM.02.02	Track when symptoms occur (AM/PM) to adjust medication	HCPs, Patient panel, Survey	High
UR.mM.02.03	Identify onset of non-motor symptoms in relation (hours apart) to medication	HCPs	High
UR.mM.03 - Notification system			
UR.mM.03.01	Optional mobile pop-up/alert when medication is due	Patient panel, Survey	High

7 Conclusions

The D2.5 report focused on user experiences and co-creation to address the needs of relevant stakeholders for the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem of digital health tools for advancing PD screening and care. The user research and co-creation processes were presented and exemplified through validated methods and a framework to ensure that all stakeholders share the same goals and priorities. To adhere to the co-creation process, a patient panel was recruited and involved in the research and design processes.

Ongoing efforts will be undertaken to collect additional data regarding users' intention to engage with the AI-PROGNOSIS ecosystem. The collected data will be systematically analyzed and disseminated through one or more peer-reviewed research publications, as well as in an upcoming relevant deliverable or project periodic report. Should any significant findings emerge during the analysis, they will be promptly communicated to the development team to inform them of the final iteration of the product.

Secondary and primary research findings are described, focusing on needs and concerns for PD screening and care that AI-PROGNOSIS aims to address. The secondary research emphasises that technologies for PD could be more patient-centric, as well as PwP wishes to use technologies to manage the complexity of their condition and, for this, seek collaboration with their medical team. Ethical considerations and privacy concerns for AI monitoring are also expressed. It is reported in the literature to be minimal sex and gender considerations in mHealth randomized controlled trials for chronic medical conditions like PD. Hence, for the ideation and co-creation process for needs mapping, the inclusion of sex and gender-balanced groups has been considered in the project.

Further presented in this deliverable are the primary research findings from focus groups, interviews, workshops, and surveys on the topics of user needs and trustworthy AI. For the secondary research findings, PwP reported that they were satisfied with their diagnosis trajectory, however, they wished they had been notified about their PD risk prior to diagnosis, and neurologist are favouring risk disclosure. It is described that PwP prefer actionable data and the potential of mitigating risk with exercise and diet changes.

The use of AI was described in the literature as a potential for more effective and personalised care. Research findings within the project identified that focus was on ethical considerations and privacy concerns for AI monitoring. This goes in line with the initial findings, where

concerns were expressed regarding the communication of the risk of acquiring PD through an app, rather than in person from an HCP. Still, the PwP would trust a doctor's treatment and diagnosis decisions which were informed by AI, but only if the reasoning is explained. The primary research findings further showed that for mAI-Health app it was important that as much data as possible should be collected automatically, reducing the input need for the users. Also, it was deemed that those at risk may need more motivation than those already diagnosed.

For mAI-Care app it was considered important with actionable data, either to act upon or to get a deeper learning from. For mAI-Insights risk-, progression-, and medication response reports were discussed. To track progression, it was important to consider daily life activities for PwP and people at risk. Symptom tracking is a most desired AI feature for all user groups. PwP believed that additional educational content would increase trust and use of AI tools. From a general perspective, the PwP welcomed AI into clinical practice as an aid.

As was made clear from the aforementioned, a defining strength of AI-PROGNOSIS has been the integration of stakeholder feedback directly into the technical development pipeline—ensuring that models and interfaces not only respond to clinical needs but reflect lived patient experience. Through iterative co-creation workshops, testing sessions, and targeted surveys with PwP, HCPs, and people at PD risk, user insights were systematically translated into functional and non-functional design priorities. These influenced everything from the timing and frequency of data collection to personalization of symptom-tracking interfaces, to ethical safeguards surrounding risk disclosure. For example, concerns regarding cognitive assessments and actionable data led to clearer visualization thresholds and opt-out mechanisms in mAI-Care. Similarly, feedback from clinicians informed the structure of mAI-Insights reports and strengthened data interpretability features, facilitating real-world usability in varied healthcare systems. This co-design approach helped optimize the AI models' clinical relevance, transparency, and patient-centered functionality—grounding algorithmic performance in context-specific use and setting a precedent for future digital health research rooted in participatory ethics.

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Appendix I Discussion Guides

I.1 Interview guide for onboarding interviews with the patient panel

Interview guide: Participation in PD Patient Panel – AI PROGNOSIS

1. Personal background

1.1 Tell us about your background. E.g. age, occupation.

2. PD Background

2.1 Diagnosis timing

- When were you diagnosed with Parkinson's disease?

2.2. Diagnosis process

- Could you briefly describe the diagnosis process?

- What steps were involved, and how did you experience it?

3. Experiences with Participation in Research and/or Patient Panels

3.1 Previous participation

- Do you have any prior experience participating in research projects or patient panels?

3.2 Experiences

- If so, could you share your experiences and what you found most meaningful or challenging?

4. Expectations and/or concerns with Participation in this Project

4.1 Expectations

- What expectations, if any, do you have about participating in this specific research project?

4.2 Concerns

- What concerns about participating in this specific research project, if any, do you have?

4.3 Hopes/Goals

- What do you hope to achieve by participating in this project?

5. View on Prediction Models Generally

(Brief introduction of the work to be done in AI-PROGNOSIS incl. the 3 planned prediction models (PD diagnosis, disease progression, and prediction of medication effect.)

5.1 General interest

- How do you view prediction models in general within healthcare and research?

5.2 Advantages and challenges

- What do you see as the specific advantages and challenges of using prediction models?

6. View on Prediction Models planned in AI-PROGNOSIS

6.1 General perspective

- What is your perspective on the use of prediction models to predict Parkinson's disease diagnosis, disease progression, and medication effects?

6.2 Specific advantages and challenges

- Are there specific advantages or challenges you see when it comes to using prediction models for PD diagnosis, disease progression, and medication effect?

7. Closing Questions

7.1 Participation and significance

- How do you perceive your own involvement in the research process, and how important do you think patients' perspectives are in such projects?

7.2 Any additional wishes

- Do you have any additional wishes or things you would like to highlight in connection with your participation in this research project?

The protocol for the focus groups with PwP (patient panel) is here provided:

Interview Guide Focus Groups: Participation in PD Patient Panel – AI PROGNOSIS

1. Personal background:

- **1.1 Background**
 - Tell us a bit about your background. E.g. age, occupation

2. PD Background:

- **2.1 Diagnosis timing**
 - When were you diagnosed with Parkinson's disease?
- **2.2 Diagnosis process**
 - Could you briefly describe the diagnosis process?
 - What steps were involved, and how did you experience it?

3. Experiences with Participation in Research and/or Patient Panels:

- **3.1 Previous participation**
 - Do you have any prior experiences participating in research projects or patient panels?
- **3.2 Experiences**
 - If so, could you share your experiences and what you found most meaningful or challenging?

4. Expectations and/or concerns with Participation in this Project:

- **4.1 Expectations**
 - What expectations, if any, do you have about participating in this specific research project?
- **4.2 Concerns**
 - What concerns, if any, do you have about participating in this specific research project?
- **4.3 Hopes/Goals**
 - What do you hope to achieve by participating in this project?

5. View on Prediction Models Generally:

- **5.1 General interest**
 - How do you view prediction models in general within healthcare and research?
- **5.2 Advantages and challenges**
 - What do you see as the specific advantages and challenges of using prediction models?

6. View on Prediction Models planned in AI-PROGNOSIS

- **6.1 General perspective**

- What is your perspective on the use of prediction models to predict Parkinson's disease diagnosis, disease progression, and medication effects?
- **6.2 Specific advantages and challenges**
 - Are there specific advantages or challenges you see when it comes to using prediction models for PD diagnosis, disease progression, and medication effect?

7. Closing Questions:

- **7.1 Participation and significance**
 - How do you perceive your own involvement in the research process, and how important do you think patients' perspectives are in such projects?
- **7.2 Any additional wishes**
 - Do you have any additional wishes or things you would like to highlight in connection with your participation in this research project?

I.2 Interview guide from data collection of HCPs

Introduction + Consent to record

- Welcome and thanks for participating.
- Who am I & what is the purpose of the interview? (To gather insights on the prioritization of features for the tools mAI-Health, mAI-Care, and mAI-Insights. Show image below.)
- Assure confidentiality and explain how the information will be used.
- Ask consent for recording.

Background

- Please briefly tell me a bit about yourself (professional role, length of time working there, etc.)
- What stage of PD are you involved in? (Prodromal/diagnosis/medication/other?)

Information about mAI-Insights HCP platform, as a platform that has three distinct modules:

- 1) PD risk monitoring module (for HCPs involved in PD screening/diagnosis)
- 2) PD progression module including condition tracking based on mAI-Care data, and progression projections (for HCPs involved in PD care)
- 3) The AIMED module, focusing on medication response prediction (for HCPs adjusting medication regimens)

1. From your perspective, what features do you envision for mAI-Insight? Please prioritize them as high/medium/low in terms of importance.

- If resources and technology limitations were not a concern, what would be your dream feature for mAI-Insight?

2. How do you envision these features impacting your work as HCP or addressing existing challenges?

- What about improving/impacting the patient experience?

Prioritization of User-Identified Features

From the two focus groups with the patient panel (9 PwP from 4 countries and various experiences related to PD diagnosis, symptoms, treatment, etc.), identified features for mAI-Health and mAI-Care were provided.

3. Please give your perspectives on these desired features by prioritizing them as high/medium/low in terms of importance and motivate why.

HCP-identified mAI-Health features

4. For mAI-Health, are there any additional functionalities you would like to see, and how would you prioritize them?

5. What criteria do you use to determine the priority of features? (e.g., impact on daily tasks, efficiency, user satisfaction)

6. Are there any specific user needs or pain points that influence your prioritization of features?

7. How would you, as a primary care HCP, like to be notified about and, if necessary, monitor the risk of a mAI-Health user?

8. How would you decide which patients should use this app?

HCP-identified mAI-Care features

9. For mAI-Care, are there any additional functionalities you would like to see, and how would you prioritize them?

10. What criteria do you use to determine the priority of features? (e.g., impact on daily tasks, efficiency, user satisfaction)

11. Are there any specific user needs or pain points that influence your prioritization of features?

Closing

- Any additional thoughts or questions?

Thank you for your time!

I.3 Introduction and instructions for the workshops with PwP (patient panel) and technical partners

Introduction to workshop 1(3)

mAI- Care

1. User Interaction:

- Persons with Parkinson's (PwP) and their caregivers interact with the mAI-Care mobile app on smartphones.

2. Data Collection:

- The app collects data from multiple sources:
 - SmartWatch-Tracked Data
 - Occasional Self-Reports on Symptoms and Condition
 - Clinical Data Shared by Attending Physician

3. PD Progression Predictive Model:

- The collected data feeds into the PD Progression Predictive Model.
- The model generates personalized projections of PD progression for the individual.

4. Symptom and Treatment Tracking:

- Users can input and track their symptoms in the app.
- Users can log information about their treatment, medication efficacy, and any side effects experienced.

5. User Interface:

- The app displays personalized projections of PD progression in an easy-to-understand format.
- Graphical representation of symptom trends and treatment effects for better visualization.

6. Clinical Data Integration:

- Integration with clinical data shared by the attending physician for a comprehensive overview of the individual's health.

7. Notification System:

- Implement a notification system to remind users to input self-reports and take medications.
- Caregivers may receive notifications or updates about the PwP's condition.

8. Data Security and Privacy:

- Ensure robust security measures to protect sensitive health data.

Introduction to workshop 2(3)

- Patient panel members and technical partners discuss together. **All contribute!**
- Mixed groups with one moderator each
- Both groups will discuss the same questions
- The breakout rooms will also be recorded

Introduction to workshop 3(3)

- Personas
 - Enable more objective way to discuss user needs
 - Complement existing patient panel perspectives
 - Feel free to refer to personas during discussions
 - Provide extra insights into extreme complexity of PD

<p>Matias Ericsson</p> <p>Jean is 87 and was diagnosed at 79. His mobility is limited, and he uses a walker to get around even in his home.</p> <p>One of his friends who has now passed away had PD, so he knows</p>		
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Further instructions for the workshops were five themes with specific questions and assignments:

T1 – Trustworthy AI design

- What makes an AI system relating to health data?

T2 – Human Autonomy in healthcare and self-care

- Would you like to be informed about the involvement of AI in decision-making in your/a persona's healthcare? If so, how?
- Would knowing that a human healthcare professional is overseeing the AI's decisions affect your level of comfort? How?
- In which situations would it be important for a human to have the final say, even if AI is used in the process?

T3 – Fairness and Equality

- How would you define fairness in AI?
- How can potential biases in healthcare delivery be addressed?

T4 – Explainability & Transparency

- Is it important to know how the AI makes predictions?
- Would understanding how the AI works make you trust its predictions more?
- What would transparency regarding how the AI makes decisions mean to you?

Q5 – Other Considerations

Are there any other considerations you believe should be prioritized when AI is used in healthcare?

I.4 Introduction and instructions for the focus groups with PwP (patient panel)

The slide features a dark blue background with white text. In the top left corner, there is the 'ai-prognosis' logo. In the bottom left corner, there is the European Union flag logo with the text 'Funded by the European Union'. In the bottom right corner, there is the text 'PwP focus group 2' and '22 February 2024'.

ai-prognosis

Focus group on user needs

Funded by the European Union

PwP focus group 2
22 February 2024

First things first

- Research participant information was sent out ahead of the meeting
- Questions?
- Record consent

Workshop agenda

1. Introductions
2. Workshop targets
3. Definitions & assumptions
4. The AI-PROGNOSIS tools
5. Discuss high-level product features and user needs (in Miro)
6. Next steps

Break when needed

3

Workshop targets

- Get an overview of app features
- Identify and prioritise user needs
- If there is time...
 - Identify and discuss potential user challenges

5

Definitions 1(2)

High-level features

- will deliver value to the end users of the AI-PROGNOSIS apps.
- Examples:
 - mAI-Health - users (persons without PD) will be able to track their risk of Parkinson's disease
 - mAI-Care - users (PwP) will be able to track disease progression
 - mAI-Insights - users (secondary care professionals) will be able to see projections of their attending patients' progression.

User needs or user requirements

- functions that the users expect/want the application to support.
- Examples:
 - The mAI-Health app users should be able to see metrics about their risk of getting PD. (Priority: Low)
 - The mAI-Care app users should be able to view when the next tasks/tests must be performed. (Priority: High).

6

Definitions 2(2)

Functional requirements

- product features or functions that developers must implement to enable users to accomplish their tasks.
- Examples:
 - The mAI-Health app must allow the user to perform a memory test (Priority: High).
 - The mAI-Care app should allow the user to choose what time of the day they receive their unperformed task reminders (Priority: Medium).

Non-functional requirements

- system qualities and constraints. They will be more or less common across the three products.
- Examples
 - UI accessibility, e.g. color contrast, text size
 - system security, e.g., encrypted databases, data transmission over HTTPs.

7

Assumptions

- Process
 - Your input will have an impact
 - Focus will be on user needs
- Products
 - The AI-PROGNOSIS tools will be based on the "study app"
 - The apps will be in both iOS & Android
 - The AI models will work perfectly

mAI- Health

High level feature

User need

- 1. User Interaction:**
 - Users interact with the mAI-Health mobile app on their smartphones.
- 2. Data Collection:**
 - The app collects data from two primary sources:
 - SmartWatch- Tracked Data
 - Self-reports on Relevant Risk Factors/Symptoms
- 3. PD Risk Assessment Model:**
 - The collected data feeds into the PD Risk Assessment Model.
 - The model calculates a quantitative PD risk score based on the input data.
- 4. Explainable Insights:**
 - The app provides explainable insights derived from the PD risk assessment.
 - Users receive understandable information about their personalized risk of acquiring Parkinson's Disease.
- 5. User Interface:**
 - The app displays the results and insights in a user-friendly interface.
- 6. Data Visualization:**
 - Visual representation of data (charts, graphs)
 - Clear presentation of the quantitative PD risk score and associated insights.

mAI- Care

1. User Interaction:

- Persons with Parkinson's (PwP) and their caregivers interact with the mAI-Care mobile app on smartphones.

2. Data Collection:

- The app collects data from multiple sources:
 - SmartWatch-Tracked Data
 - Occasional Self-Reports on Symptoms and Condition
 - Clinical Data Shared by Attending Physician

3. PD Progression Predictive Model:

- The collected data feeds into the PD Progression Predictive Model.
- The model generates personalized projections of PD progression for the individual.

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- Users can input and track their symptoms in the app.
- Users can log information about their treatment, medication efficacy, and any side effects experienced.

5. User Interface:

- The app displays personalized projections of PD progression in an easy-to-understand format.
- Graphical representation of symptom trends and treatment effects for better visualization.

6. Clinical Data Integration:

- Integration with clinical data shared by the attending physician for a comprehensive overview of the individual's health.

7. Notification System:

- Implement a notification system to remind users to input self-reports and take medications.
- Caregivers may receive notifications or updates about the PwP's condition.

8. Data Security and Privacy:

- Ensure robust security measures to protect sensitive health data.

I.5 Key questions for co-creation workshop with healthcare professionals on AI integration (AI Design & Specification workshops)

1. Understanding Clinical Needs:

- 1a: What are the most critical challenges you face in diagnosing and/or managing PD?
- 1b: How can AI-enabled solutions that estimate PD risk and prognosis fit in modern PD care and clinical practice?

2. Utility of the prediction models:

- 2a: **PD risk model:** How could an AI-driven PD risk prediction model assist you in early intervention and preventive strategies? What features or risk factors should the model prioritize to be most beneficial in a clinical setting?
- 2b: **AI's Role in PD Progression Monitoring:** How would you like AI to assist in monitoring the progression of PD, and what specific indicators would be most valuable to track?
- 2c: **Medication Response Prediction:** In what ways do you think an AI model predicting patient response to medication could improve treatment outcomes for PD?

3. Trust, Explainability and Transparency:

- 3a: What factors would help you trust AI predictions regarding PD risk and prognosis?
- 3b: How much information about the AI's internal function would you need to feel comfortable using it in clinical practice? What level of detail would you need?
- 3c: Imagine you use an AI-based software that provides estimations of PD risk for a person over time. How would you ideally like each risk estimation to be explained to you by the software?

4. Data Reliability and Quality:

- 4a: What, if any, concerns do you have about the reliability/accuracy and quality of the data used to train AI models for PD?
- 4b: How can these concerns be mitigated?
- 4c: In what ways do you think that data used for the development of AI for PD risk estimation and prognosis can be biased?
- 4d: What are some variables that we should give particular attention to, to identify potential biases, or conversely for which variables we should ensure that AI models perform equally? (Such as age, sex, etc.)

5. Impact on Patient-Doctor Relationship and Clinical Practice:

- 5a: How do you think the integration of AI in clinical decision-making will affect the patient-doctor relationship?

- 5b: Do you worry that patients might prioritize AI-driven recommendations over your professional judgment? [If yes, what features should relevant AI tools have to avoid or mitigate that?]
- 5c Do you worry that patients may not take your opinion as seriously if they know you relied on AI assistance? [If yes, what features should relevant AI tools have to avoid or mitigate that?]
- 5d: How can we ensure that AI enhances rather than undermines your role as a healthcare provider?
- 5e: In a scenario where AI for PD diagnosis support and prognosis is used in clinical practice, are you concerned about overreliance (of healthcare professionals) on those AI tools? If yes, what features should those tools have to avoid or mitigate that?

6. Responsibility and Accountability:

- 6a: How should responsibility be attributed when decisions supported by AI lead to poor or harmful patient outcomes?
- 6b: What guidelines or protocols would you suggest to clearly define accountability for decisions made with AI support in healthcare scenarios?

7. Ethical Considerations:

- 7a: Are there any other ethical concerns you foresee with the use of AI in predicting PD risk or progression or response to medication?
- 7b: How should these concerns be addressed?

8. Anything else you would like to comment or discuss?

I.6 mAI-Care UI/UX design workshops with PwP

Data visualisations

5

PD progression model

PD progression model

Values:

The total MDS-UPDRS Part 3 score which ranges from 0 to 132

6

Slowness of movement (during typing)

Slowness of movement (during typing)

Values:

Every time the user types a text of > 40 characters with the custom keyboard

7

Slowness of movement (from the smartwatch)

Values:
 Decimal number between 0-12 for each 10-min window.

Slowness of movement (from the smartwatch)

Human activity recognition

Values:
 0 (rest state) / 1 (non-rest state) for 5sec windows

Human activity recognition

Rest tremor detection and amplitude assessment

Values:
 0-4 for 2.56sec windows (corresponding to MDS-UPDRS 3.17 Rest tremor amplitude: Normal/Slight/Mild/Moderate)

Rest tremor detection and amplitude assessment

Dyskinesia detection assessment

Values:
 0 (no dyskinesia detected) / 1 (dyskinesia detected) within a window

Dyskinesia detection assessment

TOTAL
 45min
 18 Oct 2024

Balance / Posture assessment

Values:
 0-4: Normal / Slight / Mild / Moderate / Severe

Balance / Posture assessment

Active cognitive assessment

Values:
 1-3 (corresponding to MOCA Score classes: (1: 18-21 (severe), 2: 22-25 (moderate), 3: 26-30 (normal))

Active cognitive assessment

Passive cognitive assessment

Passive cognitive assessment

Values:

1-3 (corresponding to MOCA Score classes: (1: 18-21 (severe), 2: 22-25 (moderate), 3: 26-30 (normal))

App user experience

Smartwatch data sync

The mAI-Care app must inform the users if the smartwatch is not synced properly.

- | | |
|------------------------------|------------------------|
| Number of indicators: | Show indicator: |
| 1. One for all | 1. Date |
| 2. One for each | 2. Time difference |

Connection with mAI-Insights

Initiated by:

1. mAI-Care app user.
2. HCP from mAI-Insights.

Possible ways:

1. QR code or code input.
2. Code input and accept.

17

User needs questions

18

- **The mAI-Care app must allow users to choose which data to share with their caregivers.**

In which occasions would you need to share the app / data with your caregiver?

- **The mAI-Care app must provide clear motivation to the user as to why a specific type of data entry is needed.**

In which part of the app and in what way?

- **The mAI-Care app must allow the users to log sleep problems, like vivid dreams, nightmares, hallucinations etc. / Input options for relevant user data (such as menstrual cycle, psychological measures and individually relevant task data, such as 'eating soup with a spoon')**

Maybe in a "how are you feeling today?" way?

19

I.7 mAI-Care UI/UX design workshops with PwP (Updates session 1)

ai-prognosis

mAI-Health / mAI-Care requirements cocreation session

Squaredev (SQD)

Funded by the European Union

15

This slide features a dark blue background with white text. The top left corner contains the 'ai-prognosis' logo. The main title is centered in a large, bold font. Below the title, the name 'Squaredev (SQD)' is displayed. In the bottom left corner, there is a logo for the European Union with the text 'Funded by the European Union'. A small '15' and a circular logo are in the bottom right corner.

User engagement

15

This slide has a dark blue background with the text 'User engagement' centered in a large, bold, white font. In the bottom right corner, there is a small '15' and a circular logo.

User engagement

mAI-Health

- An app that facilitates data collection
- Constant user interaction not needed
- Need to periodically engage user to check correct data collection

16

This slide has a white background with dark blue text. The title 'User engagement' is at the top in a large, bold font. Below it, 'mAI-Health' is written in a smaller bold font. A bulleted list follows, containing three items. In the bottom right corner, there is a small '16' and a circular logo.

User engagement

mAI-Health

- An app that facilitates data collection
- Constant user interaction not needed
- Need to periodically engage user to check correct data collection

Considered method

- Smartwatch wear time

17

User engagement

mAI-Care

- An app that requires some user interaction
- Interaction mainly for data input

18

User engagement

mAI-Care

- An app that requires some user interaction
- Interaction mainly for data input through tasks

Main goal

- To motivate user to keep using the app and input data
- Not “punish” the user when they forget to perform a task.
- Smartwatch wear time

19

Gamification

Features:

- Turn gamified elements on/off
- Streak freeze for tasks not performed

20

Self-reporting

21

Self-reporting

Self-report sleep data & daily tasks

- Is there a need input those data?

Ways to implement it mAI-Care

- Self-report on possible sleep problems & daily tasks on x interval
- On-demand user data input

Degree of daily task difficulty

- Yes / No
- Scale of difficulty

22

I.8 mAI-Care UI/UX design workshops with PwP (Updates session 2)

Visualizations

23

Visualizations

Show only data that are actionable

Included biomarkers

- **Physical activity:** can be the number of steps, time spent in sedentary, mild or vigorous activity during the day etc.
- **Rest tremor of hand:** every 1 min when there is no gross hand movement; whether there was tremor and the level of intensity of it
- **Dyskinesias:** every TBD min; whether there was dyskinesia-like hand movement and the level of intensity of it

24

Visualizations

Considered biomarkers

- **Slowness of hand movement:** every 10 min when there is hand movement and the subject is not walking; a numerical score showing the magnitude of slowness
- **Slowness of finger movement:** every time time the virtual keyboard is used; a numerical score showing the magnitude of slowness
- **Scores of difficulty performing the specific movements:** feet stomping while seated, arising from chair, standing still, short walk) of the motor function assessment test (that uses body tracking to capture the user's movements) (every time the test is performed)

25

Visualizations

Undiscussed biomarkers

- **Night-time sleep metrics:** total sleep time and possibly other sleep metrics every night
- **RBD presence:** whether there were RBD episodes during the night
- **Daytime sleepiness:** intervals of sleep detected during the day and their duration

Unwanted biomarkers

- **Score of cognitive tests:** N-Back, Balloon-Analogue-Risk-Task and Stop-Signal tests) (every time the tests are performed)

26

Tasks performed

27

Tasks performed

Tasks for mAI-Health:

- Self-reporting questionnaires

Tasks for mAI-Care:

- Active tests
- Self-reporting questionnaires

Would seeing performed tasks be useful or just be a burden?

28

mAI-Insights UI/UX design workshops with external HCPs

Time of report generation

- Should it be generated before a scheduled visit or during the visit?
 - If beforehand, the appointment dates should be input.
 - If on demand during visit, filtering will be possible.

Daily life overview

- Input sleep data for PwP, to find out vivid dreams, nightmares, hallucinations, and/or sleep problems that develop.
 - So far, we only have RBD. Is there a specific list of symptoms that should be asked, or will it be free text?
- PwP can self-report common/key lifestyle factors (e.g., stress, diet, constipation) which can impact medication response.
 - As above, should be a specific list or free text? Also, should it be in specific intervals (e.g. every week) or daily?

2

Daily life overview

- Include 3-4 lifestyle factors and create scores based on those?
 - Should they be averaged or individual? If average, how will they be calculated?

Alerts

- To alert clinician upon "red flags" and certain deviations, e.g., increase in falls, new symptoms, hallucinations, apathy by email/other.
 - What kind of abnormalities should produce an email alert, if any or should this requirement be revised?

3

I.9 mAI-Insights UI/UX design workshops with project healthcare partners

The slide features a dark blue background on the right side with the title 'mAI-Insights UI/UX design workshop' in white. The left side is white and contains the 'ai-prognosis' logo, the European Union flag with the text 'Funded by the European Union', and the date 'February 24th, 2025'.

Feedback: please consider...

- **Overall Layout and Usability:**
 - Is the report layout intuitive and easy to navigate for a busy clinical environment?
 - Are there any suggestions you have for reorganizing the information to better support quick clinical decision-making?
- **Patient Overview:**
 - Would you like additional patient contextual information (e.g., comorbidities, symptom details) to be included?
- **Report Metadata:**
 - Is the technical information (e.g., report generation date, model version, data quality notes) presented in a way that is useful, or is it too technical for your needs?
 - Would you prefer a simplified version of these details or perhaps additional context on their clinical implications?

HCP design sprint / 24 Feb 2025

Risk screening and risk report

HCP design sprint / 24 Feb 2025

Time of report generation

- Should it be generated before a scheduled visit or during the visit?
 - If beforehand, the appointment dates should be input.
 - If on demand during visit, filtering will be possible.

Daily life overview

- Input sleep data for PwP, to find out vivid dreams, nightmares, hallucinations, and/or sleep problems that develop.
 - So far, we only have RBD. Is there a specific list of symptoms that should be asked, or will it be free text?
- PwP can self-report common/key lifestyle factors (e.g., stress, diet, constipation) which can impact medication response.
 - As above, should be a specific list or free text? Also, should it be in specific intervals (e.g. every week) or daily?

Daily life overview

- Include 3-4 lifestyle factors and create scores based on those?
 - Should they be averaged or individual? If average, how will they be calculated?

Alerts

- To alert clinician upon "red flags" and certain deviations, e.g., increase in falls, new symptoms, hallucinations, apathy by email/other.
 - What kind of abnormalities should produce an email alert, if any or should this requirement be revised?

PD screening and risk prediction system

PDF contents

The report could contain:

- Our digital PD risk score
- Top 5 determinants that influence the score and how much
- The confidence level for the prediction
- The self-reported and the confirmation of the MDS risk markers
- MDS PD risk score and the likelihood ratio of the markers
- History of other digital biomarkers tracking specific PD symptoms (e.g. bradykinesia)
- Any other insightful information

7

Name
John Doe

Age Sex Date of birth
68 M 30 / 4 / 1956

Date of Report Reporting Period
12 Jun 2025 Jan 2025 - Jun 2025

Digital risk score

Probability of having PD
58%

Level of certainty
High

Top 5 determinants

Mean of REM time
Mean of walking cadence
Level of physical activity
Mean steps / hour
Sleep efficiency

Lowers probability Increases probability

8

MDS risk score

Probability of being prodromal PD
43%

Previous probability
42%

Presence of risk MDS markers	Response	Likelihood Ratio	Reported by patient	Confirmed
Caffeine consumption	No	1.35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Never smoker	Yes	1.2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Depression	No	NA	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Possible RBD	Yes with RBDSQ	2.8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

PD screening and risk report feedback

The AI-PROGNOSIS PD screening and prediction system will generate reports accessible through the mAI-Insights web application as the mock report provided. These reports will include:

- Digital risk scores
- Explanations of the model's decision-making process
- Confidence levels
- PD risk-related digital biomarkers

→ Based on clinical utility, what is a meaningful frequency in having a report on PD risk? (For example, every 6 months)

HCP design sprint / 24 Feb 2025

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PD screening and risk report feedback

Based on the mock report which demonstrates how clinicians will interact with the model's predictions:

1. What additional elements would you like to see in the report?
2. How intuitive and easy to understand is the current format?
3. How actionable is the information presented - can you effectively use it for clinical decision-making?

HCP design sprint / 24 Feb 2025

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Progression report

HCP design sprint / 24 Feb 2025

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Progression report feedback

Prediction Details:

- Is the presentation of the predicted score, along with the confidence interval, helpful for your clinical decision-making?
- How could we better explain or visualize the prediction and its uncertainty?

Key Predictors:

- Would you like more detailed explanations or visual representations of how each predictor influences the model output?

Progression Level Indicator:

- Is the categorization (e.g., "Fast progression risk") clear and actionable?
 - Shall it be a dropdown menu to select the categorization
 - Shall we use predefined thresholds?
- Would a more nuanced grading scale or additional contextual information improve its usefulness?

Medication report

Patient Overview

- Patient name/ID: John Doe / 10234
- Age/Sex: 56 / Male
- Disease duration: 5 years (since initial PD diagnosis)
- Current medication state: ON (medication active)
- Genetic status: Sporadic (no known PD-related mutations)

2. Clinical Data Summary

PD medication breakdown:

Class	Name	Frequency	Dosage	LEDD
Levodopa	Benserazid	BD	250mg	250mg
Dopamine agonist	Mitrapex	TID	1mg	300mg
COMT inhibitor	Tolcapone	QD	100mg	125mg
Total				675mg

3. Medication outcomes summary

Levodopa: 100 mg — 250 mg

Dopamine agonist: 300 mg

MAO-B inhibitor: 25 mg

COMT inhibitor: 125 mg

Amantadine: 100 mg

Dyskinesia: 46%

Hallucinations: 8%

Sleepiness: 18%

Model Output:

- Predicted dyskinesia risk of 72%
- Key Predictors Impacting Prediction:

■ COMT inhibitor LEDD ■ Total LEDD ■ PD duration ■ Age at diagnosis ■ Other

4. Clinical Interpretation summary

The model predicts dyskinesia occurring within the next 6 months, due to the large levodopa dosage, the use of COMT inhibitors and the amount of years since PD diagnosis.

5. Report Metadata

- Report Date/Time: April 25, 2025, 14:30 CET
- Predictive Model Version: Random Forest Model v2.1

Medication report feedback

- Which other features you would like to be able to tune to see change in probabilities?
- **Outcome of interest:**
 - First occurrence of a side-effect?
 - Worsening of an effect?
 - Both
- Explainability of the outcome.

Clinical Interpretation Summary:

- Does the summary provide clear and actionable insights on the patient's expected progression/ medication response?
- Are there any aspects of the interpretation that seem vague or that you'd like to see elaborated?

I.10 mAI-Health hands-on workshops with PwP

<

Progress bar

First degree relative with Parkinson's disease

Has any of your first-degree relatives (parent, sibling, or child) been diagnosed with Parkinson's disease?

Yes

No

Not sure

I prefer not to say

Next

Profile

App version 1.0.0

Account Your doctor Settings Support

Smartwatch Enable connection with your smartwatch.

Research keyboard Activated
To deactivate the keyboard, please go to your Device Settings > Keyboard.

Data collection The app will periodically sync with the smartwatch to collect data.

Reminders Enable reminders to stay on top of your tasks.

Home Bookmarks Profile

Welcome to mAI-Health

mAI-Health helps your doctor track your risk of Parkinson's disease by using your medical history and data

Sign in Sign up

Profile

App version 1.0.0

Account Your doctor Settings Support

Your doctor

John Doe
King's college Hospital

mAI-Health automatically sends your doctor reports about your risk of Parkinson's disease. [Contact your doctor](#) to learn more.

Change doctor ^

Enter code to connect

Code **Send**

Home Menu Profile

I.11 mAI-Care hands-on workshops with PwP

← Function Motor Test

During this Comprehensive Function Motor Test, you will be asked to do a **sequence of motor tests**, including 1) Leg Agility & Arising from chair, 2) Posture, and 3) Gait.

- 1 Leg Agility Arising from chair
- 2 Posture
- 3 Gait

REM Sleep Behaviour Disorder Screening Questionnaire

In the following section you are asked to answer the following questions about your sleep behaviour.

Start

Have or have had a disease of the nervous system (e.g. stroke, head trauma, Parkinson's Disease, RLS, narcolepsy, depression, epilepsy, inflammatory disease of the brain)?

Yes

No

Please specify:

Previous **Next**

← How are you feeling?

Before you continue, we would like to know how you are feeling right now.

Right now I'm feeling:

Good motion state

Bad motion state

Don't know

Continue

Visualizations

Slowness of movement

Day Week Month Year

AVERAGE
2.06
Dec 23, 2024

Rest tremor

Day Week Month Year

Home Menu Chart Profile

Appendix II Checklist for Collaboration 2.0

Recommendations	Already doing	Will review
<p>1 Define clear aims, objectives and evaluation criteria – together</p> <p>Can help ensure that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration is evaluated and monitored in terms of its aims, objectives and effects • The problem of symbolic collaboration is reduced thanks to a clear collaborative framework • Partners with the right competencies for the task are included in relevant parts of the process • Negative effects of perspective drift are reduced through clear roles 	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>2 Confront power imbalances</p> <p>Can help ensure that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An equal and inclusive environment is created, where there is a balance of power rather than an imbalance of power • Trust in the expertise of the other collaborative partners is enhanced • All parties are actively involved and it is clear who is expected to contribute what • Knowledge exchanges take place between all parties and everyone is given the opportunity to develop their skills 	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>3 Communicate to build trust and confidence</p> <p>Can help ensure that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term relationships within the collaborative initiative are built and maintained thanks to trust-building communication • All perspectives and views are gathered through an open flow of information in all directions • A culture change takes place, thanks to the building of trust and confidence • Challenging problems get new potential solutions through open dialogue 	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Recommendations	Already doing	Will review
<p>4 Create conditions for remuneration and representativity</p> <p>Can help ensure that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Power imbalances are reduced or eliminated • More perspectives can be included through the introduction of flexible remuneration models • Key stakeholders who would otherwise be missed can be included through adaptation to individual needs of participation • Trust and belonging are promoted through the introduction of an inclusive way of working 	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>5 Build a long-term structure for collaboration</p> <p>Can help ensure that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs and time are reduced by not having to reinvent the wheel every time you need to collaborate • The problem of purely symbolic collaboration is eliminated when collaboration is a permanent feature in the organization or system • Recruiting representatives for different collaborative initiatives is easier because a structure is already in place • Trust and confidence in an organization grow if the organization signals that collaboration is such a priority that a solid structure is in place • Loss of knowledge and skills is reduced because there is a structure to manage them over time 	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>6 Share positive and negative experiences and learn from others</p> <p>Can help ensure that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Others are helped to collaborate better, leading to an improved culture of collaboration throughout society • New cross-organizational and cross-system collaborations are made possible thanks to the wide dissemination of results and experiences • A collaborative approach is normalized through open dialogue • Public understanding and interest in collaboration increase 	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Appendix III Personas

This Appendix contains the most basic iteration of the personas that will be used as a basis for the user research and co-creation activities in AI-PROGNOSIS. They are divided into three separate groups, HCP, PwP and PwoP. The latter can also be divided into two sub-categories, ICGs and at-risk individuals. While HCP can have a more complex representativity, as simultaneously HCP, PwP, and PwoP, they are treated as a separate group only representing the HCP perspective here. The pictures of the personas were generated by artificial intelligence using the online tool Canva (canva.com).

III.1 Personas for people with Parkinson's

PwP persona 1	
Persona name	Mattias Ericsson
Picture	
Backstory	<p>Mattias is a 55-year-old Swedish man working as a chief accountant in a large company. He is married and he has three children: Max (13 years old), Sara (11 years old), and Elli (6 years old). The family lives in a suburb of Stockholm. Mattias and his wife Maria both have very demanding jobs and their children also have busy schedules. As a hobby, Matthias has been playing tennis with the same group of friends twice a week for the last five years.</p> <p>Six months ago Mattias started experiencing muscle stiffness, slow movement, and sleep problems. The symptoms affected his work productivity and made it hard to play tennis and be active with his children. He got tired quickly. After a period of misdiagnosis, Mattias recently got diagnosed with Parkinson's. At first, Mattias was shocked by his Parkinson's diagnosis, and he did not know what this disease included.</p> <p>He wants to live his life in the same way for as long as possible and is interested in what he can do to reduce symptom severity, and maybe even slow disease progression.</p>
Resources	<p>Mattias is familiar with and competent in using digital tools. He uses a smartwatch and applications on his mobile to monitor his health (e.g. HR and step count). Mattias's meeting-filled schedule is hectic, making it difficult to control his medication and diet routine. His doctor emphasised exercise. However, he only has time twice a week - when he plays tennis with his friends whom he wants to keep seeing. He is unsure of what other forms of exercise he could do anyway.</p>

Emotions	<p>Mattias feels overwhelmed since his diagnosis and is uncertain about the future. He worries about not being able to work or play tennis or play with his kids anymore. He feels like a changed man and is afraid to tell his tennis buddies and colleagues about the diagnosis because he does not want people to see him differently.</p> <p>He feels like he's lost control over his life and he wants to take back control. He has read that other PwP benefitted from optimising their medication regimen, diet, and exercise. He wants to change his lifestyle so that he can feel optimal.</p>
-----------------	---

PwP persona 2	
Persona name	Marie Pinardo
Picture	
Backstory	<p>Diagnosed in her early 40s, Marie is now 56 and well versed in her routine. She is a nurse and knows a lot about PD already. She always lived a healthy lifestyle, as she knows how important it is, but now that she has PD, she makes sure to exercise daily, no exceptions. She also monitors her protein intake in relation to her medication. Marie hopes her healthy lifestyle will help keep her from progressing. She has children and is passionate about her job.</p> <p>From the outside, no one hardly notices that Marie has PD. She, however, notices that she is slower and has GI and sleep issues.</p>
Resources	<p>As an RN, Marie has pre-existing medical/health knowledge as well as access to other HCPs for questions/advice. She has access and the ability to understand scientific publications, even those with a paywall.</p> <p>Time, however, is something limited. She has a strict routine in order to manage her stressful career, healthy lifestyle, and family time.</p>
Emotions	<p>Marie can feel frustrated sometimes that she appears "normal" on the outside but feels and notices changes in her mind and body. She is however motivated to keep this healthy lifestyle and fight the progression of this disease. Her family are most important to her, and she doesn't want PD to take away her time playing with the grandchild which is on its way.</p>

PwP persona 3	
Persona name	Jean Trembley
Picture	
Backstory	Jean is 87 and was diagnosed at 79. His mobility is limited, and he uses a walker to get around even in his home.
Resources	One of his friends who has now passed away had PD, so he knows it can affect people differently. His grandson always tells him about research he has read, but Jean does not always agree or understand. Jean attends weekly online PD exercise classes with help from his grandson, who turns on the computer for him to follow along. Jean lacks technical abilities.
Emotions	He feels rather confined to the home due to mobility challenges such as freezing of gait and imbalance. He feels that he can be a burden to his family, as they often check in on him.

III.2 Personas for people without Parkinson's

PwoP persona 1	
Persona name	David Wolf
Picture	
Backstory	David has been to his family practitioner a few times over some symptoms he has been having that he read online could be PD. His MD referred him to a

	neurologist, but it is a long wait to get an appointment. Among the symptoms he's been having are fatigue, mood and cognitive changes, bradykinesia and constipation.
Resources	His wife is supportive and has been up late googling with him and observing his health. It is a long drive to the neurologist and a long wait, but they have a car. They are not very tech-savvy.
Emotions	David and his wife are worried, but having a diagnosis would be a sense of relief because they would know what is causing these new symptoms. They have not told the family about his worsened health nor about the doctor's visits, they want to first figure out what the culprit is.

PwoP persona 2 (PwoP/ICG)	
Persona name	Emma (and Erik) Thomsen
Picture	
Backstory	Emma's husband Erik has had PD for 5 years now. She helps him remember his appointments, monitor his symptoms and overall wellbeing between visits, and always attends his doctor's visits. She is recently retired.
Resources	She is very organised and good at tracking Erik's signs and symptoms. She writes down questions for the doctor, but sometimes has trouble deciphering what information is correct on the internet. She is a bit mentally drained from trying to wear multiple hats.
Emotions	Sometimes Emma finds it hard to balance being a wife with being a caretaker. Her relationship with her husband changed a lot when he got his diagnosis. Emma also has had trouble finding time for her own hobbies lately, since Erik has been having more "off" periods and so she avoids leaving him alone. She recently retired and is hoping that will create more balance.

PwoP persona 3 (PwoP/ICG/At risk)	
Persona name	Paul (and Robert) Aaldenberg
Picture	
Backstory	His father Robert was diagnosed with PD a few years back and was told that he also carries the <i>GBA</i> gene. This makes Paul very worried about his dad and his own future. He visits his dad weekly, as he lives in a nearby town. He tries to get his father to use more digital solutions for communication and monitoring of his symptoms.
Resources	He is young and adept at searching for information about his father's PD. He drives and can quickly and easily get to his father. He does not have time to join his father for medical appointments but is involved as much as possible. He finds it confusing, however, that there is so much conflicting information regarding his likelihood of getting PD passed down.
Emotions	Paul is worried he will get PD just like his father. He is also sad to see his father's mobility gradually deteriorate, as they used to hike together.

II.3 Personas for healthcare professionals

HCP persona 1	
Persona name	Susanna Lind
Picture	
Backstory	Susanna is a 44-year-old Swedish medical doctor working as a neurologist at a major university hospital in a large city in southern Sweden. She spends about 60% on clinical work and 40% on research-related tasks. She also manages the

	four research nurses at the neurology unit. Her workload is significant. Typically, the time devoted to patients coming in for return visits and patients participating in research amounts to 15-20 minutes of face-to-face time and 40-45 minutes administrative work (preparing for a visit, documenting a visit, and communicating with/distributing tasks to support staff).
Resources	Susanna is familiar with and competent in using digital tools. She uses numerous applications and systems in her daily routine. The hospital's computers and other digital tools are not always up to date, and it can take long until the newest software release is rolled out hospital wide. There is availability to technical support at the neurology unit, but waiting times are sometimes long. Susanna's English skills are excellent, and she switches between English and her native Swedish seamlessly. IT support is only available for Swedish-language software.
Emotions	Susanna is frustrated by the number of applications and programs she needs to get (and stay) familiar with just to perform her daily tasks. She delegates what she can to the unit's research nurses in order to secure more face time with patients. She is resistant to having to integrate additional digital tools into her routine.

HCP persona 2	
Persona name	Ingrid Sjöström
Picture	
Backstory	Ingrid is a 40-year-old specialised RN who has been working in neurology for 8 years. She has seen PD patients progress at all different rates and with various signs and symptoms, and wishes she could do more for her patients. She knows her staff feel the same, but they all are pressed for time and are not able to be as patient-centered as they would like.
Resources	Ingrid and her coworkers are short on time. She has familiarity with a wearable from when the department implemented a research project on home-monitoring. However, she finds it difficult to balance being a care provider with conducting research.
Emotions	The department has participated in research before, using wearables to track tremor and patient-reported variables. She likes the idea in theory but found that the tech wasted a lot of her time explaining how to use it and troubleshooting with patients when that is not their job. She sometimes feels like a “car

	<p>salesman” pushing a device her patients are uninterested in. Therefore, she is worried and skeptical about participating in research or implement new technologies again.</p>
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HCP persona 3	
Persona name	Alexandria Haglund
Picture	
Backstory	<p>Alexandria is a 50-year-old RN and PhD who has been working as the department’s coordinating research nurse for the past 6 years. She has seen PD patients progress at all different rates and with various signs and symptoms, and wishes she could do more for her patients. She got involved research because she is hoping that research will bring new solutions for her patients’ wellbeing.</p>
Resources	<p>As a manager, she spends a lot of time on paperwork, mostly electronically as the Swedish healthcare system is fairly digitalised. She is comfortable using those systems as well as home-monitoring and tele-health tools which they have used in research projects previously.</p>
Emotions	<p>Alexandria believes in research and digital solutions, that is why she got involved in research. She really enjoys it, however, it takes a lot of energy. She has to put a lot of time and effort into explaining the technology to her patients, playing tech-support, and many other tasks which she does not get credit nor any reward for. She knows it is important to ensure she does not lose any study participants. She is stressed out from the high workload. She is optimistic that the research they conduct will lead to a better future.</p>

HCP persona 4	
Persona name	Ayesha Abdeel
Picture	
Backstory	Ayesha is a 25-year-old newly hired nurse . She worked in another department for 2 years previously and is new to the neurology department. She is originally from Syria and has been living in Sweden since she was a child.
Resources	Ayesha is tech-savvy and a quick learner. She wears a smartwatch and tracks her own health metrics that way and is planning to encourage the same of her patients. She does not, however, have experience working with people with Parkinson's nor other neurodegenerative disease.
Emotions	She is excited to work in neurology now. She has a strong interest in mHealth and is looking forward to knowing more about how her new team works and what sort of research projects they are participating in.

HCP persona 5	
Persona name	Lars Limberg
Picture	
Backstory	Lars is a 30-year-old nurses aid . He has been working for about a decade and been forced into several research projects that the department decided to join.

Resources	With extensive experience in the department, Lars knows a lot about PD patients as well as technology. He is pressed for time, however, and does not earn enough to feel motivated to do any additional tasks.
Emotions	Lars has experienced the added stress of yet another task when the department conducted research. He had to explain to elderly and confused patients with severe tremor how to use an app they could not navigate. He feels that he does not get any benefit from carrying out the research tasks and has begun to just ignore them because he is fed up. He has enough on his plate and a bad enough salary as it is.

Appendix IV User needs-survey questionnaires

IV.1 Extended user needs-survey questionnaire

After each section there is also the possibility to write free-text answers as comments.

Q1: Please rate the following statements regarding the perceived potential of the AI tools within AI-PROGNOSIS in managing PD risk.

AI-PROGNOSIS tool for PD <u>risk</u> would...	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
* Increase your confidence in the AI tools' ability to accurately monitor and predict PD risk.	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Enhance your belief that AI tools could effectively manage risk factors for PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Improve your understanding and ability to act on the risk reduction recommendations provided by the AI tools.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Strengthen your belief that using AI tools could optimize efforts in managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Raise your awareness of the benefits of using AI tools for monitoring and managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
* Clarify the potential challenges associated with using AI tools for PD risk management.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Increase your belief that AI tools could address barriers in managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Increase your willingness to use AI tools for monitoring and managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Heighten your motivation to follow the risk management advice provided by AI tools.	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Enhance your sense of independence in managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q3: Please rate the following statements regarding the perceived potential of the AI tools within AI-PROGNOSIS in managing PD progression

AI-PROGNOSIS tool for PD <u>progression</u> would...	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
* Increase your confidence that the AI tools could effectively manage PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Enhance your belief that AI tools could effectively manage PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Improve your ability to understand and act on the progression management recommendations provided by the AI tools.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Strengthen your belief that using the AI tools could optimize efforts to manage PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Raise your awareness of the benefits of using AI tools for monitoring and managing PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Clarify the potential challenges associated with using AI tools for managing PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Increase your belief that AI tools could address barriers to managing PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Boost your intention to use AI tools for monitoring and managing PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Heighten your motivation to follow the progression management advice provided by AI tools.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Enhance your competence in managing PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

AI-PROGNOSIS / D2.5 Updated report on user research and co-creation

Q5: Please rate the following statements regarding the perceived potential of the AI tools within AI-PROGNOSIS in managing PD medication response

AI-PROGNOSIS tool for PD <u>medication response</u> would...	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
* Increase your confidence in using the AI tools to manage medication schedules effectively.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Enhance your belief that the AI tools could accurately monitor and predict medication response.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Improve your ability to understand and act on the medication recommendations provided by the AI tools.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Strengthen your belief that using the AI tools could optimize medication regimens.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Raise your awareness of the benefits of using AI tools for managing medication response.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Clarify the potential challenges associated with using AI tools for medication management.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Increase your belief that AI tools could address barriers to effective medication response.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Boost your intention to use AI tools for managing medication response.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Heighten your motivation to follow the medication management advice provided by AI tools.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Support your sense of competence in managing medication response.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q7: Please rate the following statements regarding the perceived usefulness of AI-PROGNOSIS in managing PD.

mAI-Health (risk monitoring) mAI-Care (progression and medication response) mAI-Insights (healthcare professional portal)	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
* The mAI-Health mobile app would be useful for early detection and notification about the risk of developing PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* The mAI-Health mobile app would provide valuable insights for managing risk factors associated with PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* The mAI-Care mobile app would be useful for monitoring the progression of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* The mAI-Care mobile app would offer valuable insights for managing treatment effects in PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* The mAI-Insights clinical platform would be useful for managing medication schedules.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* The mAI-Insights clinical platform would provide valuable recommendations to optimize medication regimens.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q8: Please rate the following statements regarding the perceived ease of use of AI-PROGNOSIS in managing PD.

mAI-Health (risk monitoring) mAI-Care (progression and medication response) mAI-Insights (healthcare professional portal)	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
* The mAI-Health mobile app would be user-friendly for monitoring the risk of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Learning to operate the mAI-Health mobile app would be straightforward.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* The mAI-Care mobile app would be user-friendly for monitoring the progression of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Using the mAI-Care mobile app would require minimal effort.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* The mAI-Insights clinical platform for healthcare professionalss appears to be user-friendly for managing medication response.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I believe it would be easy to implement the medication recommendations provided by the mAI-Insights clinical platform.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

AI-PROGNOSIS / D2.5 Updated report on user research and co-creation

Q9: Please rate the following statements regarding your attitude towards using the AI-PROGNOSIS tools in managing PD

mAI-Health (risk monitoring) mAI-Care (progression and medication response) mAI-Insights (healthcare professional portal)	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
* I have a positive attitude towards using the mAI-Health mobile app for managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I believe that the insights provided by the mAI-Health mobile app would be valuable for managing PD risk.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I have a positive attitude towards using the mAI-Care mobile app for managing the progression of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I believe that using the mAI-Care mobile app would be beneficial for monitoring PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I have a positive attitude towards using the mAI-Insights clinical platform for managing medication response.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I believe that using the mAI-Insights clinical platform would be effective for optimizing medication regimens.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q10: Please rate the following statements regarding your intention to use the AI-PROGNOSIS tools in managing PD

	Strongly Disagree 1	Somewhat Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Somewhat Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
* I intend to use the mAI-Health mobile app to monitor the risk of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I plan to utilize the mAI-Health mobile app to manage risk factors for PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I intend to use the mAI-Care mobile app to monitor PD progression.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I plan to use the mAI-Care mobile app to manage the progression of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I intend to follow recommendations from the mAI-Insights clinical platform for managing medication schedules.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I plan to adhere to the medication recommendations provided by the mAI-Insights clinical platform.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q12: Please reflect on the AI-PROGNOSIS system (including AI tools for PD risk, progression, and PD medication response) described earlier, and rate your intention to use it.

Regarding your intention to use the AI-PROGNOSIS system:	Strongly Disagree 1	Disagree 2	Neutral 3	Agree 4	Strongly Agree 5
* I intend to use the AI-PROGNOSIS system to <u>manage PD</u> .	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I plan to use the AI-PROGNOSIS system to monitor and manage the <u>risk</u> of developing PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I intend to use the AI-PROGNOSIS system to <u>track and manage the progression</u> of PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I plan to use the AI-PROGNOSIS system to <u>manage medication</u> schedule and follow the recommendations provided.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

IV.2 Short user needs-survey questionnaire

Use of technologies for Parkinson’s disease

1. Prognosis - motor condition

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
* I would be interested to know my PD prognosis in terms of future overall motor condition.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* What is your reasoning?

2. Prognosis - disease milestones

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
* I would be interested to know my PD prognosis in terms of development of future disease milestones. Possible milestones may include onset of cognitive dysfunction, hallucinations, freezing of gait, or dysphagia (swallowing difficulties).	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* What is your reasoning?

3. Actionable insights

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
* I would be interested to know which factors may affect my PD prognosis.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I would only be interested in feedback which I can act upon.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* What is your reasoning?

AI system for PD: smartphone app, smartwatch, AI

* 1. What features would you find most helpful in an AI-based tool for managing Parkinson's Disease? (Select all that apply)

- Early diagnosis (thinking back to before your PD diagnosis)
- PD risk assessment (thinking back to before your PD diagnosis)
- Personalized treatment recommendations
- Predicting disease progression
- Tracking symptoms
- Providing educational resources
- Enhancing patient and caregiver engagement
- Other

2. Privacy and trust

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
* Educational content about how the AI prediction works and uses my data would increase my trust in using the system.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I would like to choose what data from the system to share with my healthcare provider.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 3. I would like an AI-based system to track the following... (Check all that apply)

- Resting tremor (via a smartwatch)
- Slowness of finger and hand movement (via a smartwatch and smartphone)
- Dyskinesias (via a smartwatch)
- Daytime sleepiness (via a smartwatch)
- Cognitive function (via interactive tests on a smartphone)
- Balance, posture and gait (via interactive camera-based tests on a smartphone)
- I would not like an AI-based system to track (these) symptoms

4. Symptom tracking

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
* To assess my Parkinson's impact over time, I would like the system to enable me to self-select a few (2-3) activities or tasks (such as brushing my teeth or dressing) that I can track my performance of on a regular basis.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* Seeing graphs of my symptoms over time—like day by day or week by week—and alongside my daily activities would help me understand my data better.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
* I'd be willing to enter information myself—like answering questions or doing short tests—not just rely on the system to collect data automatically.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

* 5. How much time would you be willing to spend on digital tests that check your thinking or movement abilities?

- 30 min/day
- 30 min/week
- 30 min/month
- 30 min/each 6 months
- I do not want to track my symptoms on a smartphone app
- Other

6. Medication tracking

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
* I would like to have the option to enter my medication schedule and receive reminders through the app.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7. Motivators

	1 Strongly disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly agree
* Gamification (streak count, rewards) of self-tracking, e.g. for wearing the smartwatch or inputting data as much as possible, would help motivate me to consistently use the system for monitoring my PD.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7a. Are there any other gamification elements you would prefer? (Please specify)

* 8. If the AI system detected changes in your health condition (e.g. worsening symptoms or changes in prognosis), what would your desired course of action be?

- App notifies you only
- App notifies your healthcare professional but not you
- App notifies your healthcare professional who notifies you at your next doctor's visit
- App notifies you and your healthcare professional
- Other

Please add any other comments about the use of AI tools in relation to Parkinson's or on the survey itself